

The Russian-German deep-sea expedition SoJaBio (Sea of Japan Biodiversity Studies)

to the Sea of Japan onboard of the R/V *Akademik M.A. Lavrentyev*
51st Cruise, August 11th – September 5th, 2010

The Cruise Report

Marina Malyutina, Angelika Brandt, Dmitry Nekrasov & the scientific team:

Bashmanov A., Brenke N., Chizhova T., Elsner N., Golovan O., Göcke C., Kaplunenko D., Karnaukhov A., Kharlamenko V., Koptev A., Korovitskaya E., Kudryavtsev A., Lejzerowicz F., Majorova N., Miljutin D., Minin K., Popov O., Riehl T., Savelyev P., Schott T., Schwabe E., Stepanov V., Trebukhova J., Vereshagina O., Würzberg L

Introduction

The joint Russian/German expedition **SoJaBio** (Sea of Japan Biodiversity Studies) onboard of the R/V *Akademik Lavrentyev* to the deep part of the Sea of Japan started in Vladivostok on August 11th and terminated in Vladivostok on September 5th, 2010 (Fig. 1).

The project **SoJaBio** was implemented within the frameworks of the Special Russian Federal Program “World Ocean”, the programs of the Presidium of the Far-Eastern Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences (FEB RAS) “Biodiversity changes in some areas of the World Ocean with space and time”, “Marine biota response to the changes of environment and climate” and international projects and programs: “Census of the Diversity of Abyssal Marine Life” (CeDAMar) and “Circulation Research in East Asian Marginal Seas” (CREAMS) within the North Pacific Marine Science Organization (PICES). A Memorandum of Understanding was signed in Vladivostok in September 2007 by representatives of the A.V. Zhirmunsky Institute of Marine Biology (IMB), Zoological Institute and Museum (ZIM) of the University of Hamburg, and the Senckenberg am Meer, German Centre for Biodiversity Research (SAM), Wilhelmshaven.

The scientific team of the **SoJaBio** expedition included 11 Russian biologists from the A.V. Zhirmunsky Institute of Marine Biology (IMB), PIBOC FEB RAS, Vladivostok; P.P. Shirshov Institute of Oceanology RAS, Moscow, and 11 biologists from Germany, mainly from the ZIM, SAM, Berlin, München, Frankfurt am Mein, and also from Geneva, Switzerland. Moreover, 7 Russian oceanologists from the V.I. Il'ichev Pacific Oceanological Institute (PIO) FEB RAS participated in the expedition.

The goals of the **SoJaBio** expedition were:

- to study the composition, biodiversity of the benthic organisms of all size classes in the deep-sea Basin of the Sea of Japan isolated from the adjacent deep-sea areas of the Pacific Ocean;
- to compare the colonization processes, pathways and rates of colonization of the comparatively young deep-sea Basin of the Sea of Japan with the open oceanic abyssal zones;
- to study the deep-sea biogeography of the Sea of Japan, the adjacent deep-sea areas;
- to study the trophic characteristics and relations of the key species in the Sea of Japan on the background of the isolation and eutrophication of the area.
- to measure physical, chemical and biological parameters of the near-bottom deep-water layer including temperature, salinity, and oxygen saturation as well as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and methane gas concentrations which are considered to be indicators for global warming.

After few deep-sea investigations in the Sea of Japan (Derjugin, 1933, 1939; Gurjanova, 1936; Golovan, 2007; Levenstein, Pasternak, 1973, 1976; Pasternak, Levenstein, 1978; Tabachnik, 1991; Ushakov, 1955), about 30 species of invertebrates were known for the abyssal depths in this area; 21% of these species were considered to be endemic. This small degree of endemism of the benthic organisms was explained by the relatively young age of the basin (Vinogradova & Filatova, 1983). The Sea of Japan was formed in the Cenozoic as landlocked sea isolated from the Pacific. During the last glaciation it became anoxic. It was suggested that the physical peculiarities of the waters of the basin and their isolation from the abyssal Pacific resulted in scanty fauna composed of cold-adapted eurybathic species rather than true deep-sea ocean species.

Moreover, the Sea of Japan is characterised by high productivity and is influenced by anthropogenic impact. The results on species composition, abundance and diversity of epifaunal macrofauna shall be compared in future with the biodiversity of an open, non-isolated deep-sea area of the Pacific (close to the Kurile Kamchatka Trench) and with other existing deep-sea data from the Atlantic and Pacific Oceans obtained in the framework of the CeDAMar (Census of the Diversity of Abyssal Marine Life) project. During the CeDAMar expeditions the same gears were deployed following a standardised sampling methodology.

Fig. 1. Cruise track of the SoJaBio expedition

The scientific program was successfully fulfilled in spite of the loss of 8 work days: 6 days were lost because the expedition started later than planned and because of 2 days of the bad weather conditions. During SoJaBio four transects with 19 stations (stations are listed in

Table 1) at different depths (in 500, 1500, 2500, 3300 and 3600 m) have been sampled. The reason why we deployed standard set of gear is to collect the fragile organisms of all size classes and without too much damage in order to allow the best comparison possible with material already obtained in the framework of the CeDAMar projects. For logistic reasons we did not deploy a box corer (BC). The deployments of the gear were done as follows: for the multiple corer (MUC) we had 3 or 4 replicates on each station, and for the epibenthic sledge (EBS) and the Agassiz-trawl (AGT) we deployed 2 replicates per station. The CTD was deployed 35 times, the MUC – 47 times, the EBS – 25 times and the AGT – 23 times. The total working time on the deepest stations was about 40 hours including a rest time for the winch. The average time of the deployments on different depth are summarized in Table 2. Total number of collected samples is about 600. About 300 underwater pictures and video have been taken in order to document the bottom topography, sediment characteristics, food availability and input of organic matter as well as abundance of megafaunal animals. The main physical environmental parameters such as near bottom temperature, salinity, and oxygen were measured as well during the EBS deployments. The collected material was preliminarily analyzed by the each gear team and by the specialists and some preliminary results have already been prepared for this report.

Table 1. Times of deployment for the different gear used during the SoJaBio expedition.

gear/depth	1000 m	2000-2500 m	3000-3500 m
MUC (3-4)	3-4	6-8	12-15
EBS (2)	3	6	8-9
AGT (2)	3	6	8-9
CTD (2)	1	2	3
sum (h)	10-14	20-24	31-36

The expedition SoJaBio in the Sea of Japan is the first step of the joint deep-sea collaboration. We hope that the new data obtained on the biodiversity and biogeography of the Sea of Japan can be compared with other existing deep-sea data from the Atlantic and Pacific Oceans obtained in the framework of CeDAMar (Census of the Diversity of Abyssal Marine Life) and comparable data from the deep sea of the open Pacific abyssal plain in the Kurile-Kamchatka area. A follow-up German-Russian deep-sea expedition will be planned for 2012 possibly with the RV *Sonne* to the Kurile-Kamchatka area (KuramBio – Kurile Kamchatka biodiversity studies). The scientific basis of both these expeditions was introduced during a meeting of delegates negotiating the scientific and technical collaboration between Russia and Germany as planned according to the MoU.

The collected material will be scientifically shared between the Russian and German partners. The workshop “Future Visions II” (7th September 2010) will help to guarantee benefit sharing and will be used to coordinate future joint activities and collaborative research.

In order to make all results widely accessible we plan to publish the results in internationally accessible journals, including open access, synthesis papers; we will make the data of the

deep-sea biodiversity of the Sea of Japan freely available on the webpage of the Census of the Diversity of Abyssal Marine life (CeDAMar). A special volume of Deep-Sea Research II is planned for the publication of the scientific results from SoJaBio when the material is worked up scientifically.

All stations schedule

	Transect A	Depth	Gear	Remarks	Responsible
1	A1-1	212	CTD	CTD only	DDK
2	A2-1	472	CTD	finished at 3:00 UTC	DDK
3	A2-2	470	BC-1	failure	Enne S.
4	A2-3	462	BC-2	failure, sandy sed.	Enne S.
5	A2-4	486	MUC-1	7/8	Nils B.
6	A2-5	505	MUC-2	7/8	Nils B.
7	A2-6	541	MUC-3	5/8	Nils B.
8	A2-7	559	VanVeen	failure	Enne S.
9	A2-8	582	AGT-1		Christian G.
10	A2-9	wrong depht	EBS	failure	Angelika B.
11	A2-10	498	EBS	flaps not closed	Angelika B.
12	A3-1	1496	CTD	finised 17:04 UTC	DDK
13	A3-2	1496	CTD	finised 18:18 UTC, real depth 1496 (1530)	
14	A3-3	1573	VanVeen	mudy silty clay, stones	Enne S.
15	A3-4	1552	VanVeen		Enne S.
16	A3-5	1583	MUC 4	8/8	Nils B.
17	A3-6	1490	MUC 5	8/8	Nils B.
18	A3-7	1526	MUC 6	8/8	Nils B.
19	A3-8	1644	AGT-2		Christian G.
20	A3-9	1566	AGT-3		Christian G.
21	A3-10	1355	EBS 3		Angelika B.
22	A3-11	1525	EBS 4		Angelika B.
23	A4-1	1870	CTD	finished 16:31 UTC	DDK
24	A4-2	1906	CTD	finished 18:10 UTC	DDK
25	A5-1	2120	CTD	finished 20:16 UTC	DDK
26	A5-2	2101	CTD	finished 21:55 UTC	DDK
27	A6-1	2480	CTD	finished 00:23 UTC	DDK
28	A6-2	2494	CTD	finished 02:01 UTC	DDK
29	A6-3	2481	MUC-7	failure 0/8	Nils B.
30	A6-4	2490	MUC-8	failure 2/8 cores	Nils B.
31	A6-5	2511	MUC-9	failure 2/8 cores	Nils B.
32	A6-6	2481	AGT-4		Christian G.
33	A6-7	2500	EBS-5		Angelika B.
34	A6-8	2500	EBS-6		Angelika B.
35	A7-1	3380	CTD	finished 12:19 UTC	DDK
36	A7-2	3289	CTD	finished 14:44 UTC	DDK

37	A7-3	3361	MUC-10	failure 0/8 no ground contact	Nils B.
38	A7-4	3364	MUC-11	4/7	Nils B.
39	A7-5	3363	MUC-12	6/7	Nils B.
40	A7-6	3344	MUC-13	3/7	Nils B.
41	A7-7	3369	AGT/WT-5	clay block	Christian G.
42	A7-8	3054	EBS-7		Angelika B.
43	A7-9		EBS-8		Angelika B.
44	A7-10	3241	AGT-6		Christian G.
	Transect B	Depth	Gear	Remarks	Responsible
1	B1-1	3664	CTD	finished 10:55 UTC, current SW-1kn	DDK
2	B1-2	3624	CTD	finished 13:10 UTC, echosounder error=32M(1%)	DDK
3	B1-3	3665	Van Veen	failure	Nastja
4	B1-4	3665	MUC-14	7/7	Nils B.
5	B1-5	3666	MUC-15	7/7	Nils B.
6	B1-6	3666	MUC-16	7/7	Nils B.
7	B1-7	3666	EBS-9	Supra net full	Angelika B.
8	B2-1 SM		CTD		
9	B2-2 SM		CTD		
10	B2-3 SM	1765	Van Veen	failure	Nastja
11	B2-4 SM	1765	Van Veen	failure	Nastja
12	B2-5 SM	1699	AGT/WT-7		Christian G.
13	B2-6 SM		AGT/WT-8		Christian G.
14	B3-1	1600/3622	CTD	finished 11:05 UTC (20/08)	DDK
15	B3-2	3583	CTD	finished 03:31 UTC (20/08)	DDK
16	B4-1		CTD		DDK
17	B4-2		CTD		DDK
18	B4-3	3366	Van Veen	failure	Nastja
19	B4-4	3381	MUC-17	7/7	Nils B.
20	B4-5	3328	MUC-18	7/7	Nils B.
21	B4-6	3333	MUC-19	7/7	Nils B.
22	B4-7	3330	EBS-10	ok ☺	Angelika B.
23	B4-8	3336	EBS-11	ok ☺	Angelika B.
24	B5-1	2640	CTD	finished 1:56 UTC (22/08)	DDK
25	B5-2	2591	CTD	finished 08:52 UTC (22/08)	DDK
26	B5-3	2636	MUC-20	7/7	Nils B.
27	B5-4	2666	MUC-21	7/7	Nils B.
28	B5-5	2650	MUC-22	7/7	Nils B.
29	B5-6	2635	MUC-23	7/7	Nils B.
30	B5-7		EBS-12	ok ☺	Angelika B.
31	B5-8		EBS-13	Zyklon	Angelika B.
32	B5-9		AGT/WT-9		Christian G.
33	B5-10		AGT-10		Christian G.
34	B5-11		AGT-11		Christian G.
35	B6-1		CTD	finished 19:02 UTC (23/08) observed current: sw-1kn (!!!)	DDK
36	B6-2	1030	MUC-24	7/7	Nils B.
37	B6-3	1040	MUC-25	7/7	Nils B.

38	B6-4	1038	MUC-26	7/7	Nils B.
39	B6-5	1033	MUC-27	6/6	Nils B.
40	B6-6	1030	EBS-14	ok ☺	Angelika B.
41	B6-7	1000	EBS-15	ok ☺	Angelika B.
42	B6-8	1014	AGT/WT-12		Christian G.
43	B6-9	1075	AGT-13		Christian G.
44	B6-10	1026	AGT-14		Christian G.
45	B7-1	463	CTD	finished 20:48 UTC (24/08) south current	DDK
46	B7-2	486	MUC-28	6/6	Nils B.
47	B7-3	484	MUC-29	6/6	Nils B.
48	B7-4	495	MUC-30	5/6	Nils B.
49	B7-5	484	MUC-31	6/6	Nils B.
50	B7-6		EBS-16		Angelika B.
51	B7-7		EBS-17		Angelika B.
52	B7-8	532	AGT/WT-15	extremely much material !!!	Christian G.

	Transect C	Depth	Gear	Remarks	Responsible
1	C1-1	2664	CTD	finished 00:48 UTC (26/08)	DDK
2	C1-2	2645	CTD	finished 02:34 UTC (26/08)	DDK
3	C1-3	2000	CTD AS		Elsner
4	C1-4	2757	MUC-32	6/6	Nils B.
5	C1-5	2727	MUC-33	6/6	Nils B.
6	C1-6	2781	MUC-34	6/6	Nils B.
7	C1-7	2845	MUC-35	failure	Nils B.
8	C1-8		EBS-18	ok ☺	Angelika B.
9	C1-9		EBS-19	ok ☺	Angelika B.
10	C1-10	2750	AGT-16	ok	Christian G.
11	C1-11	2787	AGT-17		Christian G.
12	C2-1	3083	CTD	finished 13:21 UTC (27/08)	DDK
13	C2-2	3020	CTD	finished 15:30 UTC (27/08)	DDK
14	C3-1	3419	CTD	finished 17:45 UTC (27/08)	DDK
15	C3-2	3365	CTD	finished 19:58 UTC (27/08)	DDK
16	C3-3		EBS-20	ok	Angelika B.
17	C3-4		EBS-21	ok	Angelika B.
18	C3-5	3421	MUC-36	6/6 18:45-21:45 (28/08)	Nils B.
19	C3-6	3426	MUC-37	6/6 22:00-00:30 (28/08)	Nils B.
20	C3-7	3428	MUC-38	6/6 00:45-03:35 (29/08)	Nils B.
21	C3-8	3417	MUC-39	6/6 03:50-06:45 (29/08)	Nils B.
22	C3-9	3404	AGT-18		Christian G.
23	C3-10	3410	AGT-19	13:02	Christian G.

	Transect D	Depth	Gear	Remarks	Responsible
1	D1-1	3350	CTD	finished 15:12 UTC (29/08)	DDK
2	D1-2	3312	CTD	finished 17:57 UTC (29/08)	DDK
3	D1-3	~3350	EBS-22	finished 09:55 ok	Angelika B.
4	D1-4	3350	EBS-23	finished ok	Angelika B.

5	D1-5	3356	MUC-40	6/6	Nils B.
6	D1-6	3357	MUC-41	6/1	Nils B.
7	D1-7	3355	MUC-42	6/4	Nils B.
8	D1-8	3358	MUC-43	6/5	Nils B.
9	D1-9	3354	AGT-20		Christian G.
10	D1-10	3357	AGT-21		Christian G.
13	D2-1	2659	CTD	finished 08:33 UTC (31/08)	DDK
14	D2-2	2666	CTD	finished 10:30 UTC (31/08)	DDK
15	D2-3	2699	MUC-44	6/6	Nils B.
16	D2-4	2698	MUC-45	contact but empty, sedi.ent very soft	Nils B.
17	D2-5	2697	MUC-46	6/6	Nils B.
18	D2-6	2654	MUC-47	6/5 finished !!!!!	Nils B.
19	D2-7		EBS-24	ok ☺	Angelika B.
20	D2-8		EBS-25	ok ☺	Angelika B.
21	D2-9	2629	AGT-22		Christian G.
22	D2-10	2641	AGT-23		Christian G.

Cruise Report from oceanographers group
V.I. Il'ichev Pacific Oceanological Institute
Far Eastern Branch Russian Academy of Science
(POI FEB RAS)

1. Objectives

- 1) Obtaining standard oceanological data along the permitted route of SoJaBio expedition
- 2) Getting chemical samples in northern cold region to understand the ecological structure of the Japan Sea (using PAH detection methods) and observe methane and nitrate saturation for the mentioned region

2. Oceanographers team and its tasks

The POI FEB RAS participates in the SoJaBio cruise with the group of oceanographers which consists of 7 persons. Three of them belong to the CTD-team which is responsible for CTD-measurement (profiling of water mass structure using the high precision sea water profiler). Next three persons is responsible for the chemical analysis of Japan Sea water mass structure within the region of program. And 1 person belongs to acoustic team which maintain the ship echo-sounding system and responsible for the definition of region of work with correspondent sea bed conditions, suitable for planned works.

The program of researches POI includes measurements of physical, chemical and biological parameters of water masses in the region. This includes measurements of water temperature and salinity, oxygen saturation, biogenic matters, turbidity and fluorescence from deep layers of the sea using the Niskin bottles and CTD-rosette. The task of depth sounding (bathymetry observations) provides information about bottom surface structure of planned region of work with the 3D-model of landscape which is necessary for operation with the trawling and sediments sampling.

Name	Affiliation	Tasks
<u>Dmitry D. Kaplunenko,</u>	POI FEB RAS, PhD., senior research scientist	Chief of Oceanographers Group CTD-data processing, maintain obtained data by the groups
Alexander A. Karnaukhov	POI FEB RAS, PhD, senior research scientist,	winch operator, CTD-team
Oleg S. Popov	POI FEB RAS, engineer	CTD operation, service of equipment, CTD-team
Tatiana L. Chizhova	POI FEB RAS, research scientist	collecting samples for PAHs detection, hydrochemistry team
Elena V. Korovitskaya	POI FEB RAS, PhD, research scientist	methane content detection, hydrochemistry team
Olga Ph. Vereshagina	POI FEB RAS, PhD, senior research scientist	methane content detection, hydrochemistry team
Andrew A. Koptev	POI FEB RAS, engineer	Acoustic team, route depth ship sounding

3. Sampled parameters – Purpose and Methods

1) CTD Casting

In order to understand the circulation pattern of the Japan Sea, water masses characteristics which is typical for the area of expedition observation the SBE 9plus Underwater Unit (Manufacturer Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.) have been used together with the Rosette model 1015 (Manufacturer General Oceanics, Inc.). The latter was equipped by the 12 pcs. of Niskin bottles (the volume is 5 liters for each) for water sampling (taking samples of Methane and PAH). The main view of CTD unit together with Rosette has shown on Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. SBE 9plus with Rosette G.O.-1015 and Niskin bottles in alluminium frame.

The SBE 9plus unit was equipped by the following list of sensors (see the table.)

Name of unit	Range
Main Housing (Aluminum)	6800 meters
Digiquartz (10000 Psia) (pressure sensor)	6885 meters
DO Sensor (SBE 43) (oxygen sensor)	7000 meters
Temperature Sensor (SBE 3plus)	6800 meters
Conductivity Sensor (SBE 4C)	6800 meters
Temperature Sensor (SBE 3plus)	6800 meters
Conductivity Sensor (SBE 4C)	6800 meters
Pump (SBE 5T)	10500 meters
Pump (SBE 5T)	10500 meters
Seapoint Turbidity Meter	6000 meters
Fluorometer (Seapoint)	6000 meters
Altimeter (Benthos PSA-916D)	6000 meters

The CTD casts was made at 19 stations (all in the Russian EEZ). For the stations deeper than 1000 meters 2 casts have been made (together with MBARI-ISUS spectrophotometer, until 1000 meters and separately, until the bottom). The altimeter was installed on the CTD/Rosette system to approach the CTD as close as possible to the bottom. Generally the observed set of parameters included pressure, temperature, conductivity, salinity, oxygen, fluorescence and turbidity from the surface to about 10 meters above the bottom. Totally the 34 CTD casts have been made.

2) NO₃ profiling

The MBARI ISUS (Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute, In Situ Ultraviolet Spectrophotometer) instrument model V3 has been used for the detection of nitrate concentration in the Japan Sea during the SoJaBio cruise of the R/V “Akademik M.A. Lavrentyev” from August 11 to September 5, 2010.

The ISUS bases its results on absorption characteristics of inorganic compounds in the 200-400 nm range of the UV-spectrum. By illuminating a sample of seawater with UV light onto an UV spectrometer, the absorption spectra can be measured.

During the cruise the 19 profiles of NO₃ have been collected. The main view of ISUS has shown at Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. The MBARI-ISUS V3 with Rechargeable Battery Pack.

The measurements with MBARI-ISUS were taken during CTD-casting (together with CTD/Rosette system) in autonomous mode at all 19 stations of SoJaBio cruise. The obtained data for nitrate sensor (time dependent nitrate profiles) have been merged with the CTD-profiles to derive depth-dependent ones.

3) Methane sampling and analysing

During the SoJaBio cruise the methane sampling and analysis of its concentration in the water column and sediments have been organized. The samples of methane concentration were made using the Niskin bottles together with the Rosette system on each station of cruise observations. The further analysis was organized with the using of Portable gas chromatography detector onboard of ship. The main view of detector has been shown at fig. 3. During the cruise totally the 404 samples from water column (234) and sediments (170) have been made.

Fig.3. Portable gas chromatography detector.

4) Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) sampling

Water samples (about 6 liters per sample) were collected directly into plastic bottles. Water samples were filtered through a 0.5 µm pore glass fiber filter (Advantech GC50) to separate the dissolved phase from the particulate phase (suspended solid - SS). The filters containing SS samples were dried in the air for an hour and kept in the refrigerator at 4°C until analysis.

Extraction of PAHs in water samples: PAHs in water (4 liters per sample) were extracted by solid phase extraction using a C₁₈ cartridge (Waters Sep-Pak C-18 Cartridge). The cartridges were preconditioned with 5 mL methanol and then by 5 mL distilled water. After preconditioning, water samples were applied to the cartridges. The flow rate of sample through the cartridge was 10 mL/min. After all samples were percolated, the cartridges were dried under vacuum condition. The cartridges containing PAHs kept in the refrigerator at 4°C until analysis.

Stations, where water samples were collected (from sea surface):

A1, A3, A6, A7, B1, B2, B4, B6, C1, C2, C3, D1, D2.

In station D1 water samples were collected:

Depth, m	PAH
3300	+
3000	+
2000	+
1000	+
500	+
300	+
100	+
40	+
2	+

5) Bathymetry observations

The bathymetry observations have been made during the whole time of cruise. These observations included the depth sounding (using the ELAC echo sounder of R/V “Akademik M.A. Lavrentiev”) and its attaching to the GPS coordinates of current ship position. After completing the observation of tentative place of work the 3d surface map of the bottom were prepared for organizing of works according with the SoJaBio expedition plan.

4. Sampling summary.

St		CH ₄ (water)	CH ₄ (Sediments)	PAH	CTD casts	NO ₃ sampling
1	A1	12		2	1	1
2	A2	12	1		1	1
3	A3	12	8	2	2	1
4	A4	12			2	1
5	A5	12			2	1
6	A6	12	9	2	2	1
7	A7	12	9	2	2	1
8	B1	12	17	2	2	1

9	B2	12		2	2	1
10	B3	12			2	1
11	B4	12	20	2	2	1
12	B5	11	23		2	1
13	B6	12	9	2	1	1
14	B7	12	6		1	1
15	C1	12	19	2	2	1
16	C2	12		2	2	1
17	C3	12	18	2	2	1
18	D1	13	15	18	2	1
19	D2	18	16	2	2	1
	Total	234	170	42	34	19

6. Preliminary Results

At 19 stations CTD casting all the way to the bottom was occupied. The locations are shown in the station figure of the introduction.

Sampling with Multiple Corer (MUC) on SoJaBio. Sampling gear, method and results of sampling

DR. N. BRENKE, DR. A. KUDRYAVTSEV, F. LEJZEROWICZ, DR. D. MILJUTIN, DR. J. TREBUKHOVA

The Multiple Corer (comp. Barnett et al. 1984) is a gear designed for taking meiofauna as well as sediment samples. The employed Multiple Corer (MUC) is equipped with 8 transparent acryl-glass-cylinders, each 62cm in length, so the MUC provides up to 8 parallel, undisturbed samples per station. Each cylinder has an inner diameter of 10 cm, consequently a surface of 78.54 cm² and a height of 5 cm result in a volume of 392.7 cm³.

The regular deployment starts with lowering at 0.2 m/sec for the first 50 m of cable, then lowering with 0.5 m /sec to app. 50 m above the seafloor, where the MUC rests for about 1 minute.

During good weather conditions, lowering is proceeded with ~0.2m/sec, in bad weather faster with app. 0.5m/sec up to ground contact. After that, 5-10m of cable were added and the winch was stopped for 3 seconds.

Heaving started with 0.2m/sec, and after 50m with 0.5m/sec until the MUC is on the surface.

Within the SojaBio cruise it became clear, that the sediment of the Sea of Japan in general is very soft (presumably due to a fairly high water content of the sediment). For that reason the MUC was used with 280 kg less lead weight, compared to the standard configuration.

Figure 1: Standard 8-tube Multiple Corer (Foto:N Brenke)

Unfortunately, the tension recorder and the winch-meter were very imprecise. Therefore, position of ground contact was recorded for water depth as cable length plus 10 meters.

During the expedition, 47 deployments on 13 stations and 4 transects took place. In total 316 sediment cores were taken. Due to weather and sediment conditions only 249 sediment cores (79%) were undisturbed and used for further analyses (Table 1).

Table 1: Station list of Multi Corer deployments, gear numbers, depth and position of ground contact of SoJaBio Expedition (8/2010).

station	gear	#	region	date	depth	on ground	latitude		Longitude
				bord date	[m]	[UTC]	N	E	
A2-4	MUC	1	Sea of Japan	13.08.2010	488	16:43	44°56,7637'	137°12,0937'	
A2-5	MUC	2	Sea of Japan	13.08.2010	515	17:29	44°56,6397'	137°12,1063'	
A2-6	MUC	3	Sea of Japan	13.08.2010	550	18:19	44°56,4877'	137°12,0799'	
A3-5	MUC	4	Sea of Japan	14.08.2010	1584	10:56	44°46,4613'	137°15,0615'	
A3-6	MUC	5	Sea of Japan	14.08.2010	1473	12:55	44°48,0485'	137°15,2539'	
A3-7	MUC	6	Sea of Japan	14.08.2010	1530	14:16	44°47,6533'	137°15,3019'	
A6-3	MUC	7	Sea of Japan	14.08.2010	2481	03:45	44°20,2613'	137°23,7131'	
A6-4	MUC	8	Sea of Japan	14.08.2010	2490	06:45	44°19,9329'	137°22,9744'	
A6-5	MUC	9	Sea of Japan	14.08.2010	2511	09:00	44°19,1598'	137°23,7716'	
A7-3	MUC	10	Sea of Japan	17.08.2010	3361	16:30	43°59,8678'	137°30,2949'	
A7-4	MUC	11	Sea of Japan	17.08.2010	3346	19:20	44°00,3982'	137°30,7840'	
A7-5	MUC	12	Sea of Japan	17.08.2010	3367	21:53	43°59,9593'	137°30,9130'	
A7-6	MUC	13	Sea of Japan	17.08.2010	3344	00:43	43°59,6561'	137°31,0746'	
B1-4	MUC	14	Sea of Japan	19.08.2010	3665	18:25	42°16,54012'	136°42,1599'	
B1-5	MUC	15	Sea of Japan	19.08.2010	3665	21:45	42°16,2956'	136°44,3010'	
B1-6	MUC	16	Sea of Japan	19.08.2010	3666	03:01	42°15,8988'	136°43,5034'	
B4-4	MUC	17	Sea of Japan	21.08.2010	3381	20:00	42°59,8741'	135°25,0003'	
B4-5	MUC	18	Sea of Japan	21.08.2010	3340	02:40	43°01,1496'	135°26,1901'	
B4-6	MUC	19	Sea of Japan	21.08.2010	3333	05:45	43°01,1717'	135°26,2172'	
B5-3	MUC	20	Sea of Japan	22.08.2010	2636	04:25	43°01,6071'	135°04,3780'	
B5-4	MUC	21	Sea of Japan	22.08.2010	2666	07:24	43°02,0682'	135°04,6456'	
B5-5	MUC	22	Sea of Japan	22.08.2010	2650	10:10	43°01,7906'	135°04,5499'	
B5-6	MUC	23	Sea of Japan	22.08.2010	2635	12:20	43°01,6794'	135°04,1549'	
B6-2	MUC	24	Sea of Japan	24.08.2010	1030	09:45	43°09,7576'	135°00,8433'	
B6-3	MUC	25	Sea of Japan	24.08.2010	1040	10:36	43°09,6756'	135°00,9031'	
B6-4	MUC	26	Sea of Japan	24.08.2010	1038	11:30	43°09,7413'	135°00,9135'	
B6-5	MUC	27	Sea of Japan	24.08.2010	1034	12:27	43°09,8045'	135°00,9672'	
B7-2	MUC	28	Sea of Japan	25.08.2010	486	05:25	43°13,8712'	135°04,7522'	
B7-3	MUC	29	Sea of Japan	25.08.2010	483	06:00	43°13,9173'	135°04,8589'	
B7-4	MUC	30	Sea of Japan	25.08.2010	495	06:36	43°13,8171'	135°04,8060'	
B7-5	MUC	31	Sea of Japan	25.08.2010	484	07:15	43°13,8396'	135°04,6345'	
C1-4	MUC	32	Sea of Japan	26.08.2010	2757	05:30	42°26,1548'	133°07,6532'	
C1-5	MUC	33	Sea of Japan	26.08.2010	2709	07:55	42°26,4337'	133°08,7581'	
C1-6	MUC	34	Sea of Japan	26.08.2010	2781	10:30	42°25,9177'	133°08,2895'	
C1-7	MUC	35	Sea of Japan	26.08.2010	2841	13:00	42°25,2365'	133°07,2351'	
C3-5	MUC	36	Sea of Japan	28.08.2010	3421	09:20	42°02,1359'	133°09,9130'	
C3-6	MUC	37	Sea of Japan	28.08.2010	3426	12:15	42°02,1828'	133°10,5643'	
C3-7	MUC	38	Sea of Japan	29.08.2010	3428	15:05	42°02,1420'	133°10,8608'	
C3-8	MUC	39	Sea of Japan	29.08.2010	3417	18:15	42°02,4587'	133°09,7660'	
D1-5	MUC	40	Sea of Japan	30.08.2010	3356	05:55	41°28,4633'	131°46,8054'	
D1-6	MUC	41	Sea of Japan	30.08.2010	3358	08:50	41°28,8327'	131°47,4523'	
D1-7	MUC	42	Sea of Japan	30.08.2010	3356	11:35	41°27,2729'	131°46,7974'	
D1-8	MUC	43	Sea of Japan	30.08.2010	3358	14:25	41°28,3413'	131°47,5053'	
D2-3	MUC	44	Sea of Japan	31.08.2010	2699	11:50	42°06,0966'	131°21,8578'	
D2-4	MUC	45	Sea of Japan	31.08.2010	2698	13:55	42°06,1096'	131°21,8796'	
D2-5	MUC	46	Sea of Japan	31.08.2010	2697	15:55	42°06,0931'	131°21,8130'	
D2-6	MUC	47	Sea of Japan	31.08.2010	2654	18:03	42°06,3910'	131°21,8463'	

Nine different research groups took samples from the MUC:

- **L. Würzberg** (ZIM-HH, Germany), **A. Maiorova** & **V. Radashevsky** (IMB FEB RAS, Russia): ecology and taxonomy of macrofauna, especially Polychaeta and Sipunculida
- **V. Kharlamenko** (IMB FEB RAS, Russia) & **L. Würzberg** (ZIM-HH, Germany): trophic relationships of benthic macrofauna by stable isotope and fatty acid analyses
- **A. Bashmanov** (IMB FEB RAS, Russia): taxonomy of Ostracods
- **D. Miljutin**, **N. Brenke** (DZMB, Germany) & **Y. Trebukhova** (IMB FEB RAS, Russia) taxonomy of meiobenthic communities, especially Nematoda and Copepoda
- **N.N.** (IMB FEB RAS, Russia): sediments for granulometric analysis, TOC & Chl-a/-b
- **Kudryavtsev** (IoBZ, Germany): Protozoology, Amoebozoa and heterotrophic nanoflagellates
- **F. Lejzerowicz** (UNIGE, Switzerland): Protozoology, molecular systematics of Foraminifera
- **V. Stepanov** (PIBC FEB RAS, Russia): taxonomy of fungi and bacteria
- **O. Vereshchagina** & **E. Korovitskaya** (POI, Russia): analysis of gas components in marine sediments

For the meiofauna analyses the overlying water and the first five cm of sediment were taken. Then, the sieved water and the sediment were fixed with approximately 5% formalin.

For sediment analyses the first 10 cm of sediment, and for macrofauna, the whole core was taken. The further handling of the samples (centrifugation, sorting and distribution) will hopefully be realized in the laboratories of the Institute of Marine Biology, Far East Branch of the Russian Academy of Science, Vladivostok.

Figure 2: Upper layer of Sediment core (Foto: T. Riehl)

Consequently, only some of the MUC samples allow drawing preliminary conclusions. For any further information about the sampling process see the chapters below.

Table 2: Specification of purpose for the 8 cores per deployment of the SoJaBio Expedition (8/2010). Gray colored: core surface disturbed; -: arm destroyed; AM: Amoeba; BAC: Bacterial analysis, FO: Foraminifera; FU: Fungi; MAC: Macrofauna; MEI: Meiofauna; MEI-DESS: Meiofauna fixed in DESS; SED: Sediment; CH: sediment chemistry; ISO: Isotopes; TOC: total organic carbon

station	gear	#	core 1	core 2	core 3	core 4	core 5	core 6	core 7	core 8
A2-4	MUC	1	MEI 0-2	MEI	MEI	AM	MEI 0-2,5	MEI 0-4	empty	FO
A2-5	MUC	2	MEI	FO	MEI	MEI	MEI-DESS	MEI	empty	SED 0-20
A2-6	MUC	3	FO	MEI	empty	empty	MEI	empty	MEI	MEI
A3-5	MUC	4	MEI	MEI	SED 0-20	MEI	MEI	AM	FO	MEI
A3-6	MUC	5	MEI-DESS	MEI	SED 0-20	FO	MEI	MEI	AM	MEI
A3-7	MUC	6	MEI	MEI	MEI	MEI	MEI	CH/ISO	SED	FO
A6-3	MUC	7	empty	empty	empty	empty	empty	empty	empty	empty
A6-4	MUC	8	empty	empty	empty	empty	FO	empty	MEI	empty
A6-5	MUC	9	empty	empty	empty	empty	MEI	empty	MEI	empty
A7-3	MUC	10	empty	empty	empty	empty	empty	empty	empty	empty
A7-4	MUC	11	MEI	-	FO/SED	empty	MEI	empty	MEI	empty
A7-5	MUC	12	MEI	-	FO/SED	MEI	empty	MEI	AM	MEI-DESS
A7-6	MUC	13	FO/SED	-	MEI	empty	empty	MEI	empty	empty
B1-4	MUC	14	AM	-	MEI	SED	MEI	FO	MEI-DESS	MEI
B1-5	MUC	15	FO/SED	-	MEI	MEI	MEI	AM	MEI	MEI
B1-6	MUC	16	MEI	-	FO/SED	MEI	MEI	MEI	CH/ISO/BAC	MEI
B4-4	MUC	17	MEI	-	MEI	MEI	MEI	FO	MEI	SED
B4-5	MUC	18	AM	-	MEI	empty	FO	MEI	MEI	empty
B4-6	MUC	19	MEI	-	MEI	FO/CH/ISO	MEI	MEI	AM/SED	MEI-DESS
B5-3	MUC	20	MEI	-	MEI	MEI	FO	empty	MEI-DESS	FU
B5-4	MUC	21	FO	-	AM/SED	MAC	empty	CH/ISO	MAC	AM/FU
B5-5	MUC	22	MEI	-	AM	MEI	FO/SED	MEI	MEI	MEI
B5-6	MUC	23	MEI	-	MEI	MEI	MAC	MAC	MAC	MAC
B6-2	MUC	24	MEI-DESS	-	MEI	MEI	AM/SED	MEI	AM/FO	MEI
B6-3	MUC	25	FO/CH/ISO	-	AM/FU/SED	MEI	MEI	MEI	MEI	MEI
B6-4	MUC	26	MEI	-	MEI	MEI	FO	MEI	MEI	SED
B6-5	MUC	27	-	-	MAC	MAC	MAC	MAC	MAC	MAC
B7-2	MUC	28	-	-	MEI	MEI-DESS	AM/FO/SED	MEI	MEI	MEI
B7-3	MUC	29	-	-	MEI	MEI	MEI	AM/FU/SED	MEI	MEI

B7-4	MUC	30	-	-	MEI	MEI	MEI	MEI	MEI	empty
B7-5	MUC	31	-	-	MAC	FO	AM	MAC	MAC	MAC
C1-4	MUC	32	-	-	MEI	-	MEI	MEI-DESS	MEI	MEI
C1-5	MUC	33	-	-	MEI	-	MEI	MEI	AM/FU/SED	MEI
C1-6	MUC	34	-	-	MEI	MEI	AM/FO/SED	MEI	MEI	MEI
C1-7	MUC	35	-	-	empty	empty	empty	empty	empty	empty
C3-5	MUC	36	-	-	AM/FO	MEI	MEI	MEI-DESS	MEI	MEI
C3-6	MUC	37	-	-	MEI	MEI	MEI	MEI	MEI	AM/FU/SED
C3-7	MUC	38	-	-	MEI	AM/FO/SED	MEI	MEI	MEI	MEI
C3-8	MUC	39	-	-	AM	MAC	MAC	FO/TOC	MAC	MAC
D1-5	MUC	40	-	-	empty	empty	empty	empty	empty	CH
D1-6	MUC	41	-	-	MEI	empty	MEI	MEI	empty	FO/SED
D1-7	MUC	42	-	-	MEI	MEI	MEI-DESS	MEI	empty	FO/SED
D1-8	MUC	43	-	-	FO/FU/SED	MEI	MEI	MEI	MEI	BAC
D2-3	MUC	44	-	-	MEI-DESS	MEI	MEI	FO/SED	MEI	MEI
D2-4	MUC	45	-	-	empty	empty	empty	empty	empty	empty
D2-5	MUC	46	-	-	MEI	MEI	MEI	MEI	FO/FU/SED	MEI
D2-6	MUC	47	-	-	MEI	empty	MEI	MEI	FO/SED	MEI

Table 3: Number of different samples from all MUC stations and the number of according cores of SoJaBio Expedition (8/2010). MEI: Meiofauna; AM: Amoeba; FO: Foraminifera; SED: Sediment; others includes: BAC: Bacterial analysis, FU: Fungi; CH: sediment chemistry; ISO: Isotopes; TOC: total organic carbon; MAC: Macrofauna; ISOP: Isopods;

station	gear	#	MEI	MEI core	AM	AM core	FO	FO core	SED	SED core	other samples	others core	ISOP	ISOP core	MAC	MAC core
A2-4	MUC	1	5	#1,2,3,5,6	1	#4	1	#8	0		0		0		0	
A2-5	MUC	2	5	#1,3,4,5,6	0		1	#2	1	#8	0		0		0	
A2-6	MUC	3	4	#2,5,7,8	0		1	#1	0		0		0		2	#1,3
A3-5	MUC	4	5	#1,2,4,5,8	1	#6	1	#7	1	#3	0		0		0	
A3-6	MUC	5	5	#1,2,5,6,8	1	#7	1	#4	1	#3	0		0		0	
A3-7	MUC	6	5	#1,2,3,4,5	0		1	#8	1	#7	1	#6	0		0	
A6-3	MUC	7	0		0		0		0		0		0		0	
A6-4	MUC	8	1	#7	0		1	#5	0		0		0		0	
A6-5	MUC	9	2	#5,7	0		0		0		0		0		0	
A7-3	MUC	10	0		0		0		0		0		0		0	
A7-4	MUC	11	3	#1,5,7	0		1	#3	1	#3	0		0		0	
A7-5	MUC	12	4	#1,4,6,8	1	#7	1	#3	1	#3	0		0		0	
A7-6	MUC	13	2	#3,6	0		1	#1	1	#1	0		0		0	
B1-4	MUC	14	4	#3,5,7,8	1	#1	1	#6	1	#4	0		7	#3,5,7,6,1,	0	
B1-5	MUC	15	5	#3,4,5,7,8	1	#6	1	#1	1	#1	0		0		0	
B1-6	MUC	16	5	#1,4,5,6,8	0		1	#3	1	#3	2	#7	0		0	
B4-4	MUC	17	5	#1,3,4,5,7	0		1	#6	1	#8	0		0		0	

B4-5	MUC	18	3	#3,6,7	1	#1	1	#5	0		0		0		0	
B4-6	MUC	19	5	#1,3,5,6,8	1	#7	1	#4	1	#7	1	#4	0		0	
B5-3	MUC	20	4	#1,3,4,7	0		1	#5	0		1	#8	6	#3,4,6	0	
B5-4	MUC	21	0		2	#3,8	1	#1	1	#3	1	#6	0		2	#4,7
B5-5	MUC	22	5	#1,4,6,7,8	1	#3	1	#5	1	#5	0		0		0	
B5-6	MUC	23	3	#1,3,5	0		0		0		0		5	#3,4	4	#5,6,7,8
B6-2	MUC	24	5	#1,3,4,6,8	2	#5,7	1	#7	1	#5	0		0		0	
B6-3	MUC	25	5	#4,5,6,7,8	1	#3	1	#1	1	#3	1	#3	0		0	
B6-4	MUC	26	5	#1,3,4,6,7	0		1	#5	1	#8	0		0		0	
B6-5	MUC	27	0		0		0		0		0		0		6	#3,4,5,6,7,8
B7-2	MUC	28	5	#3,4,6,7,8	1	#5	1	#5	1	#5	0		0		0	
B7-3	MUC	29	5	#3,4,5,7,8	1	#6	0		1	#6	2	#6	0		1	#5
B7-4	MUC	30	5	#3,4,5,6,7	0		0		0		0		0		1	#3
B7-5	MUC	31	0		1	#5	1	#4	0		0		0		0	
C1-4	MUC	32	5	#3,5,6,7,8	0		0		0		0		5	#5,7	0	
C1-5	MUC	33	4	#3,5,6,8	1	#7	0		1	#7	1	#7	0		0	
C1-6	MUC	34	5	#3,4,6,7,8	1	#5	1	#5	1	#5	0		0		2	#8
C1-7	MUC	35	0		0		0		0		0		0		0	
C3-5	MUC	36	5	#4,5,6,7,8	1	#3	1	#3	0		0		0		0	
C3-6	MUC	37	5	#3,4,5,6,7	1	#8	0		1	#8	1	#8	0		0	
C3-7	MUC	38	5	#3,5,6,7,8	1	#4	1	#4	1	#4	0		0		0	
C3-8	MUC	39	0		1	#3	1	#6	0		1	#6	0		4	#4,5,7,8
D1-5	MUC	40	0		0		0		0		1	#8	0		0	
D1-6	MUC	41	3	#3,5,6	0		1	#8	1	#8	0		1	#3	0	
D1-7	MUC	42	4	#3,4,5,6	0		1	#8	1	#8	0		0		0	
D1-8	MUC	43	4	#4,5,6,7	0		1	#3	1	#3	2	#3,8	0		0	
D2-3	MUC	44	5	#3,4,5,7,8	0		1	#6	1	#6	0		0		5	#4,5,6,8
D2-4	MUC	45	0		0		0		0		0		0		0	
D2-5	MUC	46	5	#3,4,5,6,8	0		1	#7	1	#7	1	#7	0		0	
D2-6	MUC	47	4	#3,5,6,8	0		1	#7	1	#7	0		0		0	

1. Macrofauna from Multicorer samples

LAURA WÜRZBERG

Biocenter Grindel & Zoological Museum, Department of Invertebrates II, University of Hamburg, Martin-Luther-King-Platz 3, 20146 Hamburg, Germany

Intention

Sampling of fresh macrofauna samples, mainly polychaetes and sipunculids, in a good condition.

Method

For the analysis of macrofaunal organisms (e.g. fatty acids, taxonomy, anatomy), material from the MUC was taken at 5 stations (see Tabel 4). The upper 30 centimeter of cores were sieved (300µm) on ice – to keep the organisms in a fresh condition - and fixed in 6% formalin

Table 4: Amount of samples for further analysis of macrofauna.

Station	No. of cores	Remarks
B5-4	2: cores 4 and 7	
B5-6	4: cores 5, 6, 7 and 8	
B6-5	6: cores 3 - 8	
B7-5	4: cores 3, 6,7 and 8	
C3-8	4: cores 4, 5, 7 and 8	

Preliminary results

No preliminary results

Storage of samples

A.V. Zhirmunsky Institute of Marine Biology, Far East Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Vladivostok 690041, Russia. Contact person: V. Radashevsky

Study of the benthic macrofauna trophical relationships on the continental slope and abyssal of the Sea of Japan using stable isotope and fatty acid trophic markers

DR.VLADIMIR KHARLAMENKO¹ & LAURA WÜRZBERG²

¹ *A.V. Zhirmunsky Institute of Marine Biology, Far East Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Vladivostok 690041, Russia;*

² *Biocenter Grindel & Zoological Museum, Department of Invertebrates II, University of Hamburg, Martin-Luther-King-Platz 3, 20146 Hamburg, Germany*

Intention

Comparison of fatty acids and stable isotope composition of invertebrates.

Method

For the comparison of fatty acids and stable isotopes composition of invertebrates and their potential food we took the sediment and water from multicorer on some stations (Table 2,3). Sediment from the superficial layer (0– 3 cm) was taken in the tube and transferred into plastic bag using a plastic spatula. Water was collected with a siphon. For analysis of stable isotopes of C and N 5–15 g sample of sediments were dried at 60°C. For study of fatty acids composition lipids from 2-3 g sediments were extracted in a mixture of chloroform-methanol (1:1, v/v). Particulate organic matter from water column was filtered on precombusted Whatman GF/F filters (450°C for 4 h). Some filters were dried in the oven (60°C) during one

night for further stable isotope analysis while the others were placed in a mixture of chloroform-methanol (1:1, v/v) for further fatty acid analysis. In multicorer samples, the organisms were cleaner than in trawl or epibenthic sledge samples. Therefore we preferred to get the material for fatty acids or isotopic analysis from the multicorer samples, if enough material were available.

Table 5: Material taken from multicorer samples fatty acids and stable isotope composition

Station	#	Water	Sediments (0-3 cm)	Sediments (0-0.5 cm)	Invertebrates
A2			1 tube		cem. Maldanidae
A3			1 tube		
A6			1 tube		
A7			1 tube		
B1		1 tube	1 tube	1 tube	
B4			1 tube		
B5			1 tube		<i>Thyasira flexuosa</i> , <i>Pecten randolphi</i>
C3	MUC-39	3 tube	1 tube		
D1	MUC-43	1 tube	1 tube		
D2	MUC - 44				<i>Pecten randolphi</i>

Storage of samples

Final analysis of sampled material will be done in the Laboratory of Comparative Biochemistry of the Institute of Marine Biology FEB RAS and Stable Isotope Laboratory of the Far Eastern Geological Institute FEB RAS (Vladivostok, Russia).

2. Ostracods in sediments of the Japan Sea

DR. ALEXANDER BASHMANOV

A.V. Zhirmunsky Institute of Marine Biology, Far East Branch of the Russian Academy of Science, Vladivostok 690041, Russia

Intention

Collection of ostracods in sediment layers lower than 5 cm.

Method

Qualitative samples were collected using an 8-tube multicorer. The sediment column remaining in a corer after removing the upper 5-cm layer (which was used for meiobenthic studies) was washed through the sieve with 120 μm mesh size and then fixed with ethanol. For detailed list of samples, see chapter 1.

Storage of samples

All samples are stored in the A.V. Zhirmunsky Institute of Marine Biology, Vladivostok, Russia (responsible person Alexander Bashmanov).

Table 6: List of sediment samples taken

Station	Deployment of MUC
A2	
A3-6	MUC-5
A3-7	MUC-6
A6-5	MUC-9
A7-4	MUC-11
B1-4	
B4-4	
B5-5	
B5-6	
B6-3	
B6-4	
B7-3	MUC-29
B7-4	MUC-30
B7-5	MUC-31
C1-4	MUC-32
C3-5	MUC-36
D1-6	MUC-42
D2-3	MUC-44

Preliminary results

No preliminary results.

3. Quantitative collecting of Meiofauna in the deep Sea of Japan

DR. DMITRY MILJUTIN¹, DR. NILS BRENKE¹ & DR. YULIA TREBUKHOVA²

¹ Senckenberg am Meer, Deutsches Zentrum für Marine Biodiversitätsforschung (German Centre for Marine Biodiversity Research), Wilhelmshaven 26382, Germany

² A.V.Zhirmunsky Institute of Marine Biology, Far East Branch of the Russian Academy of Science, Vladivostok 690041, Russia

Intention I

Collecting quantitative samples of meiofauna for investigation on composition and distribution of meiobenthic communities.

Method I

Quantitative samples were collected using an 8-tube multicorer (Barnett et al. 1984) with an inner tube diameter 10 cm. As far as possible, for the meiobenthical purpose, 3 deployments of the multicorer were carried out at each station, and 5 cores from each deployment were used for meiofaunal studies (i.e., in optimum, 15 samples from each station in total).

750 ml plastic jars with leakproof lids were used for sample storage. Initially, the upper water layer was poured out from the core through the sieve with mesh size 40 µm, and the remains washed from the sieve into the jar with a small amount of sea water. Then the upper 5 cm of sediment were collected from the core and placed in the jars. The collected samples were fixed as they were (the sediment containing meiobenthic animals).

One corer from each station was fixed with DESS (20% dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) and 0.25 M disodium EDTA, saturated with NaCl, pH 8.0 (Seutin et al., 1991)), which is good both for morphological and genetic studies of nematodes (Yoder et al. 2006) (nematodes usually constitute 70-90% of deep-sea meiobenthos). In 1-2 hours after an initial fixation, the samples fixed with DESS were again re-fixed with DESS (the liquid content in a jar with samples was poured out through the sieve with mesh size 40 µm, and then a new amount of DESS was added). All the rest samples were fixed with 37% buffered formaldehyde in seawater. The amount of 37% formaldehyde was added to samples so that the final concentration of the formaldehyde in samples was about 4-6%.

For detailed list of samples, see chapter 1.

Storage of samples

All samples are stored in the A.V.Zhirmunsky Institute of Marine Biology, Far East Branch of the Russian Academy of Science, Vladivostok 690041, Russia. Responsible person is Dr. Julia Trebukhova.

Preliminary results

No preliminary results.

Intention II

Collecting samples of sediments for granulometric analysis and for studying of other environmental parameters in the sampling areas

Method II

The sediment samples were collected using an 8-tube multicorer (Barnett et al. 1984) with an inner tube diameter 10 cm. As far as possible, for the meiobenthical purpose, 3 deployments of the multicorer were carried out at each station, and 1 core from each deployment was used for sampling of sediments (i.e. 3 sediment samples from each station in total).

From each core, the upper 10 cm layer of sediments was collected in 10 sub-samples, each of them was representing 1 cm layer of sediments, from the first centimetre to tenth one.

Zip-lock plastic bags were used for sample storage in a freezer at -20°C.

For detailed list of samples, see chapter 1.

Storage of samples

All samples are stored in the A.V.Zhirmunsky Institute of Marine Biology, Far East Branch of the Russian Academy of Science, Vladivostok 690041, Russia. Responsible person is Dr. Dr. Julia Trebukhova.

Preliminary results

No preliminary results.

4. Unraveling the cultivable diversity of deep-sea protozoa (Amoebozoa and heterotrophic nanoflagellates)

DR. ALEXANDER KUDRYAVTSEV^{1,2,3}

¹ *Research Group Protozoology, Institute of Biology/Zoology, Free University of Berlin, Königin-Luise-Str. 1-3, D-14195 Berlin, Germany;*

² *Molecular Systematics Group, Department of Zoology and Animal Biology, University of Geneva, 30 quai Ernest Ansermet, CH-1211 Geneva, Switzerland;*

³ *Department of Invertebrate Zoology, Faculty of Biology and Soil Science, St-Petersburg State University, Universitetskaja nab. 7/9 199034 St-Petersburg, Russia*

Intention

To reveal the diversity of the cultivable Amoebozoa and heterotrophic nanoflagellates (HNF) in the deep-sea sediment samples.

Table 7: List of samples and species detected so far.

Transect	Sample #	Core #	Subsamples		Species detected
			Water	Sediment	

A	A2-4	4	A2-4/1/4 A2-4/2/4 A2-4/3/4	A2-4/4 A2-4/5 A2-4/6	<i>Cf. Massisteria sp. A2-4/1/4/1</i> <i>Filosea sp. 1 A2-4/5/1</i> <i>Cf. Caecitellus sp. A2-4/5/2</i> <i>Amoebozoa 1 A2-4/2/4/1</i>
	A3-5	3	A3-5/53		
		6	A3-5/56	A3-5/4	<i>Undet. amoeba A3-5/56/1</i>
	A3-6	3	A3-6/53		<i>Cf. Massisteria sp. A3-6/53/1</i>
		7	A3-6/57	A3-6/4	
A7-5	7	A7-5/57	A7-5/4		
B	B1-4	1	B1-4/51	B1-4/4	
	B1-5	6	B1-5/56	B1-5/4	<i>Cf. Caecitellus sp. B1-5/56/1</i>
	B4-5	1	B4-5/51	B4-5/4	
		5	B4-5/55		
	B4-6	7	B4-6/57	B4-6/4	
	B5-4	3	B5-4/53		
		8	B5-4/58	B5-4/4	
	B5-5	3	B5-5/53	B5-5/4	<i>Cf. Caecitellus sp. B5-5/53/1</i> <i>Filosea sp. 1 B5-5/53/2</i>
		5	B6-2/55	B6-2/4	
	B6-2	7	B6-2/57		
		1	B6-3/51		
	B6-3	3	B6-3/53	B6-3/4	
		5	B7-2/55		
	B7-2	5	B7-2/55		
	B7-3	6	B7-3/56	B7-3/4	
B7-5	5	B7-5/55	B7-5/4		
C	C1-5	7	C1-5/57	C1-5/4	
	C1-6	5	C1-6/55		
	C3-5	3	C3-5/53		
	C3-6	8	C3-6/58	C3-6/4	
	C3-7	4	C3-7/54		
	C3-8	3	C3-8/53	C3-8/4	

Method

To avoid contamination of the samples from the surface, cores were closed from the top with ethanol-sterilized plugs, and further subsamples were taken with sterile tools. The water layer over the sediment surface was collected using a silicon tube. A small remaining portion of the water layer mixed with the uppermost layer of the sediment was collected using a syringe. In addition, a subcore of the upper 3 cm of the sediment was taken using a cut syringe and sliced into 1-cm layers. The collected material was introduced into the enrichment cultures in Petri dishes with addition of sterilized seawater and wheat grains. Cultures were incubated at room temperature and regularly observed using an inverted microscope. The protists detected were subcultured by transferring into the Petri dishes with fresh sterile seawater and wheat grains.

Storage and further processing of the samples

Cultures derived from the samples will be brought alive to the research group Protozoology of the Free University of Berlin for further detailed light and electron microscopical studies as well as sequencing the genetic markers necessary for identification. Remaining samples in enrichment cultures will be concentrated and brought into the same laboratory to check if further growth and detection of more protistan species is possible.

5. Morphological characterization and phylogenetic reassessment of Foraminifera

PhD student FRANCK LEJZEROWICZ
University of Geneva

Intention

Foraminifera studies for the SoJaBio cruise will be both morphological characterization and ribosomal small subunit-based (SSU rDNA) phylogenetic reassessment of this fast evolving micro-eukaryotic group. Given the situation of the Japan Sea basin and the trend of Foraminifera to diversify rapidly, the retrieved material may contain novel species of interest. Along with the growing foraminiferal SSU rDNA database available, additional sequences may also help to review the whole phylogeny of this very ancient, phylum and its position within the eukaryotic Tree of Life.

For ecological and biogeographic studies of Foraminifera across the Japan Sea, after specific PCR amplications, foraminiferal environmental diversity will be analyzed through cloning and sequencing and/or using massive pyrosequencing. This strategy will be applied to the total retrotranscribed environmental RNA pool, thus providing a confident overview of living species. Either as a groundtruth or simply to compare, foraminiferans stained by Rose Bengal (i.e. alive during sampling) will also be sorted for each station.

Method

Half of the surface sediment (0-2cm depth) of each core was sub-sampled, for up to three cores per station. The first core was sub-sampled for three purposes: i) RNA, 1 to 2g with a sterile, RNA-free scalpel blade, mixed in LifeGuard solution (MoBio), stored at 4°C, ii) Rose Bengal, 5g with a clean spoon and iii) sorting of living specimen, remaining sediment affordable sieved with cooled sea water through 500, 125 and 63 µm meshes, the two small fractions being screened in the lab. Isolated and identified (family level at least), each single specimen was fixed in guanidine isothiocyanate for preparation of PCR-ready DNA solutions (620 tubes), in 96° ethanol (119 tubes) and/or 4% formaline (76 tubes) for further morphological analysis, or in ethanol only if not abundant species. The two other cores of each station were sub-sampled for species sorting and fixation only (third step above).

Table 8: Qualitative summary of RNA and Rose Bengal stained sediments (X : 1 tube) and app. Number of species.

Station #	A2			A3			A6			A7			B1			B4			B5			B6			B7			C1			C3			D1			D2										
Cast #	4	5	6	5	6	7	3	4	5	3	4	5	6	4	5	6	4	5	6	3	4	5	6	2	3	4	5	2	3	4	5	4	5	6	7	5	6	7	8	5	6	7	8	3	4	5	6
Nbre of cores	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
RNA	X			X			X			X			X			X			X			X			X			X			X			X			X			X			X				
Rose Bengal	X			X			X			X			X			X			X			X			X			X			X			X			X			X			X				
Species	12			10			4			8			6			13			15			18			16			5			8			6			14										

Storage of samples

All samples were brought to the University of Geneva at Jan PAWLOWSKI's lab (Molecular Systematics Group). Prone to a rapid decay, RNA samples have to be processed immediately, that is retrotranscribed in cDNA. DNA from each fixed specimens will be extracted and stored at -20°C. Rose Bengal stained sediments will be stored at room temperature until sorting.

Preliminary results

The phylogenetic position of some morphological groups is not clearly established. This is especially the case for monothalamous foraminiferans, a group that comprises nearly all specimens obtained from the deepest stations. Relatively to the very rich shallower stations, these stations (>2500m) are poor and nearly depleted in calcareous species. Most diversity was found below 1500m, gathering species belonging to more than 10 different families.

6. Collecting of marine fungi and bacteria

VLADIMIR STEPANOV

Pacific Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry, Far East Branch of the Russian Academy of Science, Vladivostok, Russia

Intention

Collecting of sediment samples from a multicorer for studying of taxonomic composition of marine fungi and bacteria

Method

Samples were collected using an 8-tube multicorer. For studies of fungi, about 3-5 cm³ of upper sediment layer in a corer was taken, placed into a plastic bag and stored in a freezer at -20°C. For studies of bacteria, about 3-5 cm³ of upper sediment layer in a corer was taken, placed into vial and then stored in a refrigerator at +4°C.

For detailed list of samples, see chapter 1.

Storage of samples

All samples are stored in the Pacific Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry, (Vladivostok, Russia), in the laboratory of microbiology (chief - Dr. V.V. Mikhajlov, person responsible for samples: Vladimir Stepanov).

Preliminary results

No preliminary results.

Tabel 9: List of cores species detected so far.

Station-deployment	Deployment of MUC	Corer, No.	Sample for fungi	Sample for bacteria
A6-3	MUC-7	No data	+	
A6-4	MUC-8	No data	+	
A7-4	MUC-11	No data	+	
A7-6	MUC-13	No data	+	
B1-4	MUC-14	No data	+	

B1-5	MUC-15	4	+	
B4-4	MUC-17	4	+	+
B4-5	MUC-18	1	+	
B5-3	MUC-20	8	+	+
B5-4	MUC-21	8	+	
B6-2	MUC-24	8	+	
B6-3	MUC-25	1	+	+
B6-4	MUC-26	3	+	
B7-2	MUC-28	5	+	+
B7-3	MUC-29	6	+	
C1-5	MUC-33	7	+	+
C3-5	MUC-36	3	+	+
C3-6	MUC-37	8	+	
C3-7	MUC-38	4	+	
D1-6	MUC-41	8	+	
D1-7	MUC-42	8	+	+
D1-8	MUC-43	8	+	
D2-5	MUC-46	7	+	+
D2-6	MUC-47	7	+	

7. Gas components in marine sediments of the Sea of Japan

DR. OLGA VERESHCHAGINA & DR. ELENA KOROVITSKAYA

V.I.II'icheov's Pacific Oceanological Institute, Vladivostok, Russia

Intention

Sampling for an analysis of gas components (methane, oxygen, nitrogen, and carbon dioxide) in marine sediments

Method

The sediments were sampled using 8-tube multicorer. One core was usually used from each multicorer deployment. The sediment column containing the sediment layer lower than 5 cm was used for gas sampling (the upper 5 cm layer was used for sampling of meiobenthos).

The sediments were sampled from different sediment layers with 12 ml plastic syringes (Figure 3), then transferred into 68 ml glass airtight vials filled with a saturated water solution of NaCl containing NaN_3 .

After transferring the sediments, air bubbles were removed from the vials through the rubber

Figure 3: Sampling a sediment core from MUC -17 with plastic syringes.

caps using the hollow needle. Then the vials were placed in a pure helium medium, so that the NaCl saturated solution by helium when the former was sucked out with the syringe. After that, the vials containing sediments were stirred well during 4 hours for getting a gas balance, and then were injected into the gas chromatograph “Kristall – Luxe 4000M” (Russia). For detailed list of samples, see chapter 1.

Fig. 4: Methane concentration in different layer of sediments for 3 deployments of multicorer (preliminary results).

Preliminary results

For the methane concentration in different layer of sediments, see the Fig. 3. An abnormal high methane concentration was found at the D-2 station

Tabel 10: Methane concentration of the different MUC stations.

Station and deployment of MUC	Depth of sediment layer, cm	Volume of sediments sampled, ml	CH ₄ , μl/(l·K)				
A2-6 MUC-3	6	10	0,329798658	B6-2 MUC-24	8,5	11,3	0,976133012
A3-5 MUC-4	5	10,6	0,68448778	B6-2 MUC-24	14	12	1,303720539
A3-5 MUC-4	38	12	4,415637584	B6-2 MUC-24	22	12	3,033333333
A3-6 MUC-5	10	8,4	0,484228188	B6-3 MUC-25	8,5	11,8	0,644992296
A3-6 MUC-5	22	10,4	1,775838926	B6-3 MUC-25	17	12	1,194949495
A3-6 MUC-5	26	11,8	2,897383688	B6-3 MUC-25	27	12	1,911919192
A3-7 MUC-6	11	12	1,392483221	B6-4 MUC-26	4	11	0,330909091
A3-7 MUC-6	27	12	3,023154362	B6-4 MUC-26	15	12	0,735353535
A6-4 MUC-8	7	12	0,054966443	B6-4 MUC-26	26	12	2,454242424
A6-4 MUC-8	15	11,8	0,037265385	B7-2 MUC-28	8,5	9	1,441342282
A6-4 MUC-8	25	11,2	0,15704698	B7-3 MUC-29	7,5	10	1,055355705
A6-4 MUC-8	37	11,4	0,39537266	B7-3 MUC-30	7,5	10	1,110322148
A6-5 MUC-9	7	12	0,403087248	B7-3 MUC-31	2,5	12	0,540503356
A6-5 MUC-9	15	12	0,43057047	B7-3 MUC-31	7,5	11,2	1,403607383
A6-5 MUC-9	25	12	0,74204698	B7-3 MUC-31	12,5	10,6	1,856413828
A6-5 MUC-9	34	12	1,200100671	B7-3 MUC-31	8	11,8	0,279490388
A6-5 MUC-9	40	12	1,566543624	C1-4 MUC-32	16,5	11,8	0,968900011
A7-4 MUC-11	7	11,4	0,019221968	C1-4 MUC-32	25	11,8	2,263872142
A7-4 MUC-11	20	12	0,027391304	C1-4 MUC-32	32	9	2,919328859
A7-4 MUC-11	30	11,2	0,097826087	C1-4 MUC-32	40	10	0,589892617
A7-4 MUC-11	42	11,6	0,236131934	C1-4 MUC-32	50	11,8	6,549391423
A7-5 MUC-12	9	8,8	0,037351779	C1-4 MUC-32	60	12	0,800067114
A7-5 MUC-12	11	8,3	2,824934521	C1-4 MUC-32	7,5	11,5	0,353697111
A7-5 MUC-12	11	12	0,118103161	C1-5 MUC-33	15	11,8	3,363201001
A7-6 MUC-13	11	12	0	C1-5 MUC-33	25,5	11,4	7,444577888
A7-6 MUC-13	11	12	0	C1-5 MUC-33	35	11,8	10,92807417
A7-6 MUC-13	9	10,3	0	C1-5 MUC-33	42,5	11,8	13,99315209
B1-4 MUC-14	16	11,5	0,03791941	C1-5 MUC-33	49	11,4	16,23920876
B1-4 MUC-14	22	10,8	1,978480311	C1-5 MUC-33	6,5	11,8	0,34505218
B1-4 MUC-14	30	11,2	1,265391015	C1-6 MUC-34	17	11	1,15045653
B1-4 MUC-14	42	11	3,369656633	C1-6 MUC-34	24	12	1,678165939
B1-5 MUC-15	7,5	11,8	0,083149553	C1-6 MUC-34	34	12	2,1
B1-5 MUC-15	12	11,8	0,009238839	C1-6 MUC-34	41	11,4	2,529073776
B1-5 MUC-15	19	10,8	2,467111111	C1-6 MUC-34	47,5	12	2,457641921
B1-5 MUC-15	32	12	8,372	C3-5 MUC-36	8	11,8	0
B1-5 MUC-15	41	12	11,6662	C3-5 MUC-36	13	7,2	0,076599327
B1-5 MUC-15	52	11	16,83665455	C3-5 MUC-36	18	11,2	0,049242424
B1-6 MUC-16	7	18,1	0	C3-5 MUC-36	26	11,4	0,029027113
B1-6 MUC-16	17	12	0,1456	C3-5 MUC-36	33	11,4	0,125784157
B1-6 MUC-16	24	11	0,059563636	C3-5 MUC-36	40	11,5	0,076732543
B1-6 MUC-16	30	10,6	1,710113208	C3-5 MUC-36	47	11	0,120330579
B1-6 MUC-16	39	11	3,841854545	C3-6 MUC-37	8	11,8	0,065434001
B1-6 MUC-16	46	10,6	5,686641509	C3-6 MUC-37	13	8,5	0,012976827
B4-4 MUC-17	7,5	11,8	0,009254237	C3-6 MUC-37	18	12	0,073535354
B4-4 MUC-17	17	12	0,8099	C3-6 MUC-37	30	12	0,101111111
B4-4 MUC-17	21	11,8	1,887864407	C3-6 MUC-37	38	12	0,284949495
B4-4 MUC-17	27,5	12	2,7209	C3-6 MUC-37	48	12	0,588282828
B4-4 MUC-17	34	12	3,3033	C3-7 MUC-38	9	11	0,120330579
B4-4 MUC-17	43	12	5,9969	C3-7 MUC-38	14	9	0,085791246
B4-4 MUC-17	50	12	7,28	C3-7 MUC-38	18	10,8	0,112345679
B4-5 MUC-18	7	12	0,2093	C3-7 MUC-38	25	12	0,551515152
B4-5 MUC-18	12	11,7	1,073333333	C3-7 MUC-38	37	12	1,387979798
B4-5 MUC-18	19	11,8	2,637457627	D1-5 MUC-40	2,5	13,8	0,119693095
B4-5 MUC-18	26,5	11,8	4,71040678	D1-5 MUC-40	5	15,2	0,239071207
B4-5 MUC-18	35	11,7	7,009333333	D1-5 MUC-40	7	11,8	1,157168495
B4-5 MUC-18	45	11,4	9,875894737	D1-6 MUC-41	7	18,6	0,348711842
B4-6 MUC-19	7	10,8	0,101111111	D1-6 MUC-41	17	11,6	0,132677621
B4-6 MUC-19	15	11,4	0,823789474	D1-6 MUC-41	23	11	0,569652227
B4-6 MUC-19	24	8,4	2,028	D1-6 MUC-41	30	11,8	1,052747128
B4-6 MUC-19	34	11,8	3,220474576	D1-6 MUC-41	42,5	11,8	1,54651348
B4-6 MUC-19	39	12	4,1041	D1-6 MUC-41	51	11,6	1,78167091
B4-6 MUC-19	46	12	4,7502	D1-7 MUC-42	6	11,6	0,502279565
B4-6 MUC-19	53,5	11,8	6,172576271	D1-7 MUC-42	16	11,8	1,583778865
B5-3 MUC-20	8	8,8	0,455844156	D1-7 MUC-42	26	11,8	2,273188488
B5-3 MUC-20	17	10,6	1,324528302	D1-7 MUC-42	36	11,8	2,850801957
B5-3 MUC-20	27	9,6	1,961607143	D1-7 MUC-42	46	11,6	3,203216848
B5-3 MUC-20	37	11,8	2,540193705	D1-7 MUC-42	56	12	3,398758389
B5-3 MUC-20	45	11,5	3,304099379	D2-3 MUC-44	6	11,8	0,801205779
B5-3 MUC-20	55	11,8	3,588377724	D2-3 MUC-44	15	12	3,421661074
B5-4 MUC-21	3,5	11,5	0,368198758	D2-3 MUC-44	26	11,4	29,99046273
B5-4 MUC-21	11	12	1,158743633	D2-3 MUC-44	34,5	10,6	50,6002406
B5-4 MUC-21	18	12	1,909609508	D2-3 MUC-44	40	11,8	63,03439882
B5-4 MUC-21	25	12	2,359830508	D2-3 MUC-44	44	11,2	74,60713087
B5-4 MUC-21	34	12	3,109423729	D2-5 MUC-46	6	11,8	2,329086566
B5-4 MUC-21	43	12	3,797055838	D2-5 MUC-46	13	11,8	10,35977704
B5-5 MUC-22	7	10,2	0,19564049	D2-5 MUC-46	18	10	13,01605369
B5-5 MUC-22	15	12	0,443451777	D2-5 MUC-46	25	11,6	26,47866235
B5-5 MUC-22	25	12	1,237969543	D2-5 MUC-46	34	11,8	36,17537254
B5-5 MUC-22	34	11	2,025768343	D2-6 MUC-47	6	11,8	1,84463656
B5-5 MUC-22	42	10,8	3,387478849	D2-6 MUC-47	11	11,6	8,226012497
B5-5 MUC-22	50	12	3,372081218	D2-6 MUC-47	16,5	11,8	15,09248095
B5-6 MUC-23	7	11	0,423294878	D2-6 MUC-47	24	11,8	29,43965419
B5-6 MUC-23	15	12	1,071675127	D2-6 MUC-47	30	11,6	39,72747049
B5-6 MUC-23	25	12	1,579796954				
B5-6 MUC-23	36	12	2,069441624				
B5-6 MUC-23	45	12	2,540609137				

Summary

Applying 1 Multicorer on 4 transects, 5 scientists took on 13 stations, with 47 deployments in 87 hours, 249 sediment cores, and separated 317 samples of a surface area of 19557 cm² or a sediment volume of 64402 cm³, in a total depth of 113723 meters, using 227916 meters of wire.

☺

References

- Barnett, P.R.O., Watson, J., Connolly, D. (1984) A multiple corer for taking virtually undisturbed samples from shelf, bathyal and abyssal sediments. *Oceanologica Acta* 7, 399-408.
- Seutin, G., White, B.N., BOAG, P.T. (1991) Preservation of avian blood tissue samples for DNA analyses. *Canadian Journal of Zoology-Revue Canadienne de Zoologie* 69, 82-90.
- Yoder, M., Tandigan De Ley, I., King, I.W., Mundo-Ocampo, M., Mann, J., Blaxter, M., Poiras, L., De Ley, P. (2006) DESS: a versatile solution for preserving morphology and extractable DNA of nematodes. *Nematology* 8(3), 367-376.

Investigations of the epifaunal macrofauna using the epibenthic sledge during the Sea of Japan Biodiversity Studies (SoJaBio) expedition

Angelika Brandt¹, Nikolaus Elsner¹, Torben Riehl^{1,2}, Marina Malyutina³, Olga Golovan³, Thorsten Schott⁵, Enrico Schwabe⁴, Laura Würzberg¹

¹*Biocentre Grindel and Zoological Museum, Martin-Luther-King-Platz 3, 20146 Hamburg, Germany, abrandt@zoologie.uni-hamburg.de*

²*DZMB Senckenberg, c/o Biocentre Grindel and Zoological Museum, Martin-Luther-King-Platz 3, 20146 Hamburg, Germany, triehl@senckenberg.de*

³*A.V. Zhirmunsky Institute of Marine Biology, Far East Branch of Russian Academy of Sciences (FEB RAS). Vladivostok 690041, Russia, m_malyutina@mail.ru*

⁴*Bavarian State collection of Zoology, Münchhausenstraße 21, 81247 München, Germany Enrico.Schwabe@zsm.mwn.de*

⁵*Oktopus GmbH, Company for Applied Research, Innovative Technologies and Services in Ocean Research, Kieler Str. 51, 24594 Hohenwestedt, Germany <schott@oktopus-maritech.de>*

Objectives:

One of our major objectives for the epibenthic macrofauna was to study abundance and species richness of stations along the different transects in the Sea of Japan. We generally hypothesize a decline in abundance and increase in species richness with distance from shore and with depth. While all samples will be sorted at a high taxon level, we will focus our preliminary analysis on the general composition of selected suprabenthic samples and especially peracarid crustaceans.

In close cooperation with Drs. Marina Malyutina and Olga Golovan, we plan to focus on deep-sea Isopoda (Crustacea Malacostraca), which were obtained in high numbers using a newly designed epibenthic sledge.

Questions which we aim to solve and hypotheses we want to prove are:

Specific

- What is the benthic deep-sea isopod species composition and biodiversity in the Sea of Japan? We hypothesize that it differs from adjacent deep-sea basins.
- Do we find new species for that area and can we describe abundance, species richness, evenness? We hypothesize that species richness and evenness are lower than in adjacent basins.
- Is endemism increased in the deep sea of the Sea of Japan due to the isolation if compared with adjacent deep-sea areas? We hypothesize that this is the case.
- Do abundance and species richness of Isopoda decrease at stations with increasing distance from the shore and with increasing depth? We hypothesize that abundance decreases and species richness increases.
- Can we identify geographic patterns in species composition in the Sea of Japan and the adjacent deep sea (compare α -diversity with β -diversity)? We hypothesize that α -diversity differs from β -diversity.

- How is the world-wide geographic distribution of the species and higher taxa of the Sea of Japan? We hypothesize that the endemism is high and that β -diversity will be low. We think that on species level we will not find much similarity to the adjacent deep-sea areas, however, on genus level we will.

Work at sea:

An epibenthic sledge (EBS) especially designed for sampling small epifauna of a few mm to one cm of size at any depth and on any substrate was used. It has been deployed 24 times at four transects (see general introduction of cruise report) successfully. It is equipped with a supra- and epibenthic sampler possessing plankton nets with a cod end as described by Brandt & Barthel (1995) and Brenke (2005). The main purpose of the EBS is to catch animals. It is one of the most effective gears to sample macrofauna in high numbers and qualitatively well preserved for any morphological or ecological investigation (due to the cod ends with its valves, see Brenke 2005). In order to improve our understanding of the behaviour of the EBS on the ground and to try to analyse the seafloor at the same time while we catch animals, we have now constructed a newly designed EBS which has a laterally enlarged frame for the fixation of an Aanderaa CTD and a video and still camera. This new EBS now enables us to obtain additional data on temperature, salinity, pressure, conductivity, oxygen concentration besides images of the seafloor and the quality of the sediment when the sledge is hauled over the ground. During SoJaBio the new EBS is deployed for the first time and will receive its certificate from the *German Lloyd* based on the first deployments during this expedition.

For the EBS deployment the ship had to steam 0.5-3.5 nautical miles (depending on the water depth, see table) prior to the CTD position. We usually deployed the EBS using 1.5 times the cable length to water depth. While the EBS was lowered with 0.5 m/sec. the vessel had to compensate the speed of the wire (for example, 0.5 m/sec. lowering = ship made 1 knots) until the EBS reached the ground. When the cable length reached 1.5 the length of the water depth, hauling was done for 10 minutes. After 10 minutes ship stopped at end of hauling and winch started to holster the EBS with 0.5 m/sec. while the vessel remained on position until EBS was back on deck of the *Akademik Lavrentyev*. The haul distances were calculated using. The tension meter of the winch indicated when the gear left the ground. Because the haul lengths varied, for the comparative analysis the data will be standardised to 1000m hauls, what is equivalent to a bottom area of 1000 m² sampled by the sledge. On deck the complete samples will be immediately transferred into pre-cooled 96% ethanol and kept at least for 48 h in -20°C for DNA studies. With the Aanderaa data, the trawling time can be determined precisely using the tilt sensor (time on ground) and the current meter (start of trawling). With the trawling time and ship speed during trawling, the trawling distance was calculated.

a

b

Fig. 1 a & b Epibenthic sledge

EBS #	station	state	date	time	depth [m]	haul start	haul end	from bottom camera	vic
EBS 1	A2-9	failure	13.08.2010						
EBS 2	A2-10	successful	14.08.2010	23.46-0.28	455-465	44°56.9197N 137°11.8947E	44°57.0966N 137°12.0732E	44°57.0193N 137°11.9896E	x
EBS3	A3-10	successful	14.08.2010	20.55-22.37	1354-1356	44°49.8620N 137°13.9974E	44°50.0210N 137°14.0932E	44°50.2803N 137°14.2177 E	x
EBS 4	A3-11	successful	14.-15.8.2010	23.27-1.11	1494-1525	44°47.6338N 137°15.3182E	44°47.8110N 137°15.3922 E	44°48.1762N 137°15.3039 E	x
EBS 5	A6-7	successful	16.08.2010	12.17-15.13	2511-2534	44°19.4270N 137°24.1964E	44°19.2650N 137°24.1206E	44°18.7422N 137°24.0524E	x
EBS 6	A6-8	successful	16.08.2010	16.00-18.45	2545-2555	44°18.6270N 137°24.4079E	44°18.4712N 137°24.3985E	44°18.3034N 137°24.0370E	x
EBS 7	A7-8	successful	17.08.2010	19.10-2.22	3345-3357	44°00.8871N 137°29.7822E	44°00.7933N 137°29.8060E	44°00.7933N 137°30.2780E	x
EBS 8	A7-9	successful	18.08.2010	0.42-4.25	3340-3347	44°00.8871N 137°29.7822E	44°00.1668N 137°31.3496E	43°59.9124N 137°31.7745E	x
EBS 9	B1-7	successful	19.08.2010	18.33-19.15	3665-3666	42°15.5533N 136°43.2772E	42°15.7357N 136°43.3044E	42°15.9748N 136°42.8880E	x
EBS 10	B4-7	successful	21.08.2010	20.47-21.31	3298-3353	43°01.5063N 135°26.4484E	43°01.3831N 135°26.3669E	43°00.9932N 135°26.1730E	x
EBS 11	B4-8	successful	21-22.8.2010	1.27-2.08	3312-3334	43°01.3440N 135°28.0092E	43°01.2126N 135°28.1308E	43°00.7508N 135°28.5344E	x
EBS 12	B5-7	successful	23.08.2010	5.12-5.50	2661-2688	43°01.6964N 135°05.2859E	43°01.7360N 135°05.4958E	43°01.7389N 135°05.9690E	x
EBS 13	B5-8	successful	23.08.2010	8.50-9.27	2609-2655	43°01.3064N 135°05.9562E	43°00.9363N 135°06.5366E	43°00.9363N 135°06.5366E	x
EBS 14	B6-6	successful	25.08.2010	1.07-1.28	970-994	43°10.6362N 135°00.8476E	43°10.4546N 135°00.8247E	43°10.2744N 135°00.7990E	x
EBS 15	B6-7	successful	25.08.2010	2.49-3.09	1001-1011	43°10.3999N 135°00.9751E	43°10.2513N 135°00.9239E	43°10.1336N 135°00.8996E	x
EBS 16	B7-6	successful	25.08.2010	19.18-19.33	517-521	43°13.4229N 135°04.2286E	43°13.5581N 135°04.3569E	43°13.6089N 135°04.3934E	x
EBS 17	B7-7	successful	25.08.2010	20.26-20.42	470-528	43°13.4578N 135°04.3295E	43°13.5809N 135°04.1939E	43°13.6318N 135°04.1490E	x
EBS 18	C1-8	successful	27.08.2010	7.05-7.47	2670-2681	42°26.5832N 133°09.1471E	42°26.6230N 133°09.3740E	42°26.7298N 133°09.7430E	x
EBS 19	C1-9	successful	27.08.2010	10.52-11.02	2693-2725	42°26.4275N 133°08.6525E	42°26.4636N 133°08.8737E	42°26.5707N 133°09.4842E	x
EBS 20	C3-3	successful	28.08.2010	11.00-11.42	3431-3435	42°01.3458N 133°09.7454E	42°01.2359N 133°09.8746E	42°01.0547N 133°09.9003E	x
EBS 21	C3-4	successful	28.08.2010	15.41-16.10	3427-3431	42°01.5613N 133°09.5741E	42°01.4637N 133°09.7381E	42°01.4637E 133°09.8288E	x
EBS 22	D1-3	successful	30.08.2010	7.57-8.35	3355-3357	41°28.3497N 131°46.6929E	41°28.1326N 131°46.4722E	41°27.9058N 131°46.2575E	x
EBS 23	D1-4	successful	30.08.2010	12.15-21.55	3356	41°28.7198N 131°46.7702E	41°28.6028N 131°46.6796E	41°28.3427N 131°46.5050E	x
EBS 24	D2-7	successful	01.09.2010	9.15-9.47	2619-2637	42°07.1711N 131°21.1091E	42°07.0405N 131°21.0345E	42°06.8608N 131°20.9826E	x
EBS 25	D2-8	successful	01.09.2010	12.38-13.35	2653-2683	42°06.6051N 131°21.0149E	42°06.4555N 131°20.9308E	42°06.1140N 131°20.7726E	x

Table 1: EBS station table

Preliminary results:

On board the supranets of transect A from about 500, 1500, 2500 and 3350 m depth were sorted to higher taxon (class/order) level. The results of the most important and numerous taxa are presented in Table 2 and Figures 2 and 3. In general, for example Bivalvia, Amphipoda, Cumacea and Mysidacea occurred in higher numbers on the shelf and their numbers decreased with increasing depth. Polychaeta, Isopoda, and Tanaidacea, on the contrary, increased in abundance with increasing depth (Table 2 and Figure 2).

With regard to the Peracarida of Transect A, Amphipoda were most numerous and occurred with 49 % of all peracarids, however, their main occurrence was at the shallowest station in 500 m. Isopoda occurred with 44 % of all peracarids and were most numerous at the deepest station, where *Eurycope spinifrons* Gurjanova, 1936 (Munnopsidae) occurred in high numbers. Tanaidacea (5 % of all peracarids) were also most frequent at the deepest station and Mysicacea and Cumacea were rare (1 %) and mainly occurred at the shallowest station (Figure 3a).

Figure 3 b documents that the numbers of Peracarida were generally higher at 500 and 3350 m and lower at 1500 and 2500 m. This could be due to a steeper slope which might not allow the accumulation of sufficient food for the peracarid crustaceans. In general, Amphipoda are dominating the shallowest station and Isopoda the deepest station.

Sorting of the supranets from transect C (C1-8; C 3-3) supported the general taxon composition documented for transect A. For example, numbers of Isopoda and Polychaeta are relatively high at the deep stations, but do not reach the high values of transect A. It will be interesting to analyse whether this might be due to a higher anthropogenic impact (pollution) along transect C compared to A.

Most of the Isopoda belonged to the Asellota, and the families Munnopsidae and Desmosomatidae were most frequent, however, also Munnidae, Paramunnidae, and the flabelliferan family Bopyridae occurred in the samples.

Characteristic photographs of the deep seafloor are presented in Figure 4 and the first preliminary measurements of the Aanderaa CTD at bottom are summarised in Table 3.

Phylum	Class/Order N	A2-10-S 500m	A3-10-S 1350 m	A6-7-S 2500 m	A7-8-S 3350 m
Porifera		7	3	42	uncounted
Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	3	6		
	Anthozoa			182	140
Ctenophora		21			
Nemertea		13	1		
Nematoda		15	150		
Mollusca	Bivalvia	136	36	21	9
	Gastropoda	49	18	28	8
	Scaphopoda		1		
	Aplacophora	4	5		
Annelida	Polychaeta	352	172	229	1309
Sipuncula	Sipunculida	10	1		
Crustacea	Ostracoda	746	2		1
	Copepoda	11409	253	1	
	Amphipoda	1778	103	156	2
	Isopoda	526	40	55	1768
	Tanaidacea	174	27	2	226
	Cumacea	1158	31	48	
	Mysidacea	27	4	7	
	Euphausiacea	983			
Chelicerata	Decapoda	15	5		
	Pycnogonida				
	Acari	2			
Bryozoa		4			
Echinodermata	Asteroidea	3	2		
	Echinoidea	5	13		
	Ophiuroidea	882	98	505	8
Chaetognathia	Crinoidea	4			
		409	3		27
	warms	37	20	2	
	misc.	44	10	15	5

Table 2: Specimens of taxa retrieved from supranet samples. Taxa marked in yellow decrease in abundance with increasing depth, taxa marked in pink increase in numbers with increasing depth.

EBS #	station	bottom temperature (°C)	max. pressure (kPa)	max. depth (m)	bottom conductivity (mS/cm) *	bottom O ₂ -concentration (µM) *	bottom current (cm/s)	trawling distance (m)	fixativ
EBS 1	A2-9	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
EBS 2	A2-10	0,791 ± 0,015	4851,957	475	29,331 ± 0,014	259,424 ± 0,777	8,065 ± 2,802	369	ETOH
EBS3	A3-10	0,196 ± 0,001	13971,026	1387	29,201 ± 0,072	226,435 ± 0,755	4,189 ± 1,826	437	ETOH
EBS 4	A3-11	0,195 ± 0,006	15130,351	1503	29,264 ± 0,110	223,743 ± 1,034	2,533 ± 0,859	346	Formaline
EBS 5	A6-7	0,224 ± 0,002	25014,389	2491	29,674 ± 0,145	225,537 ± 0,590	6,019 ± 2,549	599	ETOH
EBS 6	A6-8	0,223 ± 0,001	25142,469	2504	29,660 ± 0,105	225,018 ± 1,089	3,625 ± 1,896	854	Formaline
EBS 7	A7-8	0,281 ± 0,001	33430,156	3333	30,106 ± 0,026	223,910 ± 0,345	5,728 ± 0,733	508	ETOH
EBS 8	A7-9	0,289 ± 0,005	33530,945	3343	30,122 ± 0,106	223,477 ± 0,384	4,123 ± 0,860	543	Formaline
EBS 9	B1-7	0,317 ± 0,001	36869,133	3677	30,219 ± 0,035	222,558 ± 0,228	8,416 ± 1,210	725	ETOH
EBS 10	B4-7	0,281 ± 0,001	33141,289	3304	30,110 ± 0,034	224,974 ± 0,650	2,670 ± 0,804	489	ETOH
EBS 11	B4-8	0,282 ± 0,001	33266,258	3317	30,123 ± 0,049	224,643 ± 1,102	2,201 ± 0,943	709	Formaline
EBS 12	B5-7	0,237 ± 0,001	26438,486	2634	29,758 ± 0,041	226,103 ± 0,958	4,770 ± 1,517	459	ETOH
EBS 13	B5-8	0,240 ± 0,006	26372,736	2627	29,761 ± 0,082	226,017 ± 1,307	2,021 ± 1,030	681	Formaline
EBS 14	B6-6	0,396 ± 0,006	9720,758	962	29,247 ± 0,005	240,086 ± 0,280	4,620 ± 2,009	170	ETOH
EBS 15	B6-7	0,380 ± 0,007	10134,617	1003	29,274 ± 0,011	238,963 ± 0,437	5,414 ± 1,225	169	Formaline
EBS 16	B7-6	0,664 ± 0,016	6346,22	625	29,286 ± 0,009	264,487 ± 2,208	n/a	457	ETOH
EBS 17	B7-7	0,664 ± 0,005	6324,238	622	29,284 ± 0,018	263,506 ± 1,241	n/a	327	Formaline
EBS 18	C1-8	0,237 ± 0,001	27523,484	2742	29,813 ± 0,033	227,237 ± 1,305	2,625 ± 1,203	463	ETOH
EBS 19	C1-9	0,239 ± 0,003	27569,705	2747	29,815 ± 0,054	227,212 ± 0,704	2,032 ± 1,178	474	Formaline
EBS 20	C3-3	0,296 ± 0,003	34419,445	3432	30,110 ± 0,077	223,547 ± 0,463	1,690 ± 0,943	600	ETOH
EBS 21	C3-4	0,294 ± 0,001	34424,516	3432	30,120 ± 0,028	223,551 ± 0,360	2,432 ± 1,647	247	Formaline
EBS 22	D1-3	0,288 ± 0,001	33699,875	3360	30,071 ± 0,042	224,210 ± 0,866	2,414 ± 1,133	482	ETOH
EBS 23	D1-4	0,287 ± 0,0005	33700,09	3360	30,076 ± 0,039	224,252 ± 1,077	3,100 ± 1,210	301	Formaline
EBS 24	D2-7	0,230 ± 0,005	26347,830	2625	29,759 ± 0,046	227,878 ± 0,707	1,820 ± 0,947	324	ETOH
EBS 25	D2-8	0,231 ± 0,003	8710,708	861	29,766 ± 0,051	227,531 ± 0,712	2,178 ± 0,051	807	Formaline

Table 3: Data measured by Aandera SEAGUARD. Mean current speed was calculated from ground contact to trawling start. Mean temperature, mean conductivity and mean O₂-concentration was calculated from ground contact to leaving the ground. * The Aanderaa data for conductivity and O₂-concentration showed a constant deviation from the data obtained by the SBE 9+ which is most likely due to the steel frame.

Fig. 2: Specimens of most numerous taxa (uncorrected numbers) of transect A with depth.

Fig. 3 a: Percentage of Peracarida from all stations of transect A.

Fig. 3 b: Composition of Peracarida from at stations of transect A.

Figure 4: Deep-sea floor of Transect A from 500-3350 m.

Barcoding Deep-Sea Isopoda

Preliminary sorting of the supra-net cod end of the epibenthic sledge indicates a relatively poor diversity of isopods at the sampled deep-sea stations: Only one species occurred but in very high abundances: *Eurycope spinifrons* Gurjanova, 1933 (Asellota: Munnopsidae). Contrastingly, the shallow stations offered a higher diversity on family and species level. Consequently the number of species recognized for DNA barcoding is only very small for abyssal and lower bathyal stations but higher for shelf and upper bathyal (see Table 4).

Table 4: Numbers of species and individual specimens recognized for the Senckenberg project “Barcoding Deep-Sea Isopoda”.

Station	Depth [m]	Family	No of species	No. ind.
A2-10	~460	Bopyridae	1	1
		Desmosomatidae	3	36
		Gnathiidae	1	1
		Munnidae	1	1
		Munnopsidae	4	32
		Paramunnidae	1	6
A3-10	~1350	Desmosomatidae	3	13
		Munnopsidae	2	8
		Paramunnidae	1	1
A6-7	~2520	Munnopsidae	1	14
A7-5	~3350	Munnopsidae	1	1
A7-8	~3350	Munnopsidae	1	12
B1-4		Munnopsidae	1	3
B4-7		Munnopsidae	1	2
B4-8		Munnopsidae	1	5
B5-3		Munnopsidae	1	6
B5-6		Munnopsidae	1	4
C1-4		Munnopsidae	1	6
C1-6		Munnopsidae	1	1
C1-8		Munnopsidae	1	7
C3-3		Munnopsidae	1	6
D1-3	~3360	Munnopsidae	1	14
		Total	cf. 13	180

The high abundances of *E. spinifrons* (see figure 5) across transects and stations (i.e. geographic distance and depth), however, make a survey of intraspecific genetic variability possible in a – for deep-sea species - unique way. The analysis of genetic homogeneity across those scales will help to uncover levels of genetic heterogeneity and possibly identify different haplotypes. This will lead to answers to questions about applicability of DNA barcoding on deep-sea isopods and evolutionary processes in deep-sea species, such as: Is there one stable population in the sampled area? Or did we find genetically highly divergent populations? Does a radiation take place in the deep Sea of Japan? Tissue will be processed possibly within the next twelve months, depending on accessibility of the samples and availability on travel grants, in cooperation with the project “DNA Barcode of Life” at the Smithsonian Institution, Washington, D.C. These studies are part of the Ph.D. thesis of Torben Riehl.

Figure 5: *Eurycope spinifrons*. More than 1500 specimens from the EBS supra-net cod end at station A7-8. © Torben Riehl.

A total of ca. 50 isopods were sampled in order to conduct PCR gut content analyses utilizing specific foraminiferan primers. From deep stations, ca.30 specimens of the munnopsids *Eurycope spinifrons* and ca. 10 of *Baeonectes* sp. were collected, and from shallower stations, ca. 10 specimens each were sampled of the munnopsid *Eurycope* sp. and the desmosomatid *Eugerda* sp.

To find out more about the role of foraminiferans in macrobenthic diets, 8 foraminiferan species (*Cibicides* spec., *Oolina* spec., *Ovaminna* spec., *Hyponepinella* spec., *Phainogullmia* spec., *Elphidium* spec., *Uvigerina* spec. and *Nonionella* spec.) were sampled (picked and identified by Franck Lejzerowicz, further determination of species will follow after examination in the home laboratory). Samples of one species were pooled (ca. 10 – 135 specimens) and stored in chloroform/ethanol (2:1) at -20°C until analyses in the laboratory of V. Kharlamenkov and S. Kiyashko. Their fatty acid signatures will be compared to macrobenthic organisms (particularly isopods and scaphopods) to reveal possible feeding on foraminiferans. These studies are part of the Ph.D. thesis of Laura Würzberg

Cruise-report for the Agassiz-Trawl (AGT) during the Expedition SoJaBio

Christian Göcke¹, Vladimir Kharlamenko², Kirill Minin³, Pavel Savelyev², Enrico Schwabe⁴, Laura Würzberg⁵

¹*Forschungsinstitut und Naturmuseum Senckenberg, Senckenberganlage 25, 60325 Frankfurt/Main, Germany. corresponding author, e-mail: christian.goecke@senckenberg.de*

²*Zhirmunsky Institute of Marine Biology, Far East Branch of Russian Academy of Sciences (FEB RAS). Vladivostok 690041, Russia.*

³*Shirshov Institute of Oceanology of Russian Academy of Sciences, Nakhimovskiy ave., 36, 117997 Moscow, Russia.*

⁴*Bavarian State collection of Zoology, Münchhausenstraße 21, 81247 München, Germany*

⁵*Biocenter Grindel & Zoological Museum, Department of Invertebrates II, University of Hamburg, Martin-Luther-King-Platz 3, 20146 Hamburg, Germany.*

Objectives: The Agassiz trawl (AGT) was used during the SoJaBio-Expedition to catch megafauna (animals larger than 1 cm, even though within batches of sediment, also some macrofauna was usually caught). Preliminary results given here therefore concern only megafaunal components in the Sea of Japan.

Methods: During the SoJaBio Expedition, two different trawls were deployed to catch megafaunal elements (see Tab. 1 for detailed information on deployments). While one was a typical Agassiz trawl (AGT, see Fig. 1a) with 350 cm x 70 cm (width x height) and a mesh size of 10 mm, the other trawl was modified Agassiz-trawl (WT, Fig. 1b), with 135 cm x 60 cm and an inner net at the end with a mesh size of 10 mm. Because of its stronger outer net, it proved to be more sufficient on shallow stations with rocky substrate, whereas on deeper stations it was not as efficient as the AGT due to the smaller opening and wider mesh sizes in the front part of the net.

Fig. 1: Gears used for trawling: a) large Agassiz trawl (AGT), b) small bottom trawl (WT)

Trawling process: First, the trawl was set into water, than wire was given with 0.5 m/s winch speed until a cable length of 1.5 times the water depth was reached. During this process, the ship was moving with about one knot. After cable was put out, the winch was stopped and the hauling process started, which lasted 2 to 20 minutes, depending on the depth and gear (AGT/WT respectively), with the ship moving at about one knot. After the end of the hauling, the trawl was pulled back with about 0.5 m/s. During this process, the ship moved with about 0.5 knots. While trawling, the time, position and depths at the following key points were recorded: from board, at bottom, haul start, haul end, from ground, on deck. Trawled distance was calculated from the mean ship speed and the trawling time between the points “haul start” and “from ground”.

Sorting and fixation of catches: After the catch was on board, sediment was superficially checked for fragile animals and a picture of the whole sample including a station label was taken. Afterwards the sediment was sieved in 1 mm and 300 µm fractions, all visible animals were removed and sorted according to major taxa (see preliminary taxa list, Appendix). The majority of animals was fixed in 96% ethanol, where it was more appropriate, formalin-seawater (6%) was used. Some subsamples were also frozen for biochemical analysis. If sieve remains had a high potential for macrofauna, they were also fixed for further analyses. Specimen numbers were either counted, or estimated (for high individual numbers) while sorting. “Highlights” of each catch were usually photo-documented.

AGT subsamples, including freeze-samples for biochemistry, were taken for the following institutions:

- Zhirmunsky Institute of Marine Biology, Far East Branch of Russian Academy of Sciences (FEB RAS). Vladivostok. **IMB**. Here the major part of the collection is to be stored.
- Bavarian State collection of Zoology, München, Germany
- Shirshov Institute of Oceanology of Russian Academy of Sciences, Moscow, Russia.
- Biocenter Grindel & Zoological Museum, Department of Invertebrates II, University of Hamburg, Martin-Luther-King-Platz 3, 20146 Hamburg, Germany
- Forschungsinstitut und Naturmuseum Senckenberg, Frankfurt/Main, Germany

A full list of subsamples and their deposition/storage has been prepared and is available from Marina Malyutina and Christian Göcke.

Preliminary results:

During the SoJaBio Expedition, a total of 23 trawls were deployed (Tab. 1), seven with the small bottom trawl (WT) and 16 with the AGT. Trawled distances range from 88 m up to 570 m. These differences are due to complications in controlling the ship speed at slow speeds and to inconsistencies in given cable length and duration of hauling process, which were partly induced by communication problems with the responsible staff at the winch. Bathymetrically sampled stations range from depths between 530 and 3400 m with a preference on deeper stations.

Table 1: Stations list for trawls.

Station	Position haul start		Position From Ground		Depth [m]:	Calculated trawled distance [m]	Gear	Date
	Latitude N	Longitude E	Latitude N	Longitude E				
A2-8	44°56.5158	137°13.5771	44°56.0262	137°13.2535	582	570,4	AGT	13.08.2010
A3-8	44°46.9605	137°14.7863	44°47.3829	137°15.0065	1623	539,5	AGT	14.08.2010
A3-9	44°47.9016	137°14.4724	44°48.2025	137°14.6596	1566	344,5	AGT	14.08.2010
A6-6	44°19.4165	137°22.2995	44°19.1298	137°22.2386	2481	293,9	WT	15.08.2010
A7-7	43°59.1003	137°28.9119	43°58.7685	137°28.7189	3369	414,8	WT	17.08.2010

A7-10	44°00.4004	137°29.5230	44°00.1299	137°29.3448	3213	447,6	AGT	18.08.2010
B2-5	42°33.5977	136°17.2561	42°33.5243	136°17.5619	1699	321,0	WT	20.08.2010
B2-6	42°33.9916	136°16.1348	42°33.8376	136°16.6237	1705	566,7	WT	20.08.2010
B5-9	43°01.7724	135°05.0182	43°01.8896	135°05.1625	2350	242,0	WT	24.08.2010
B5-10	43°01.7149	135°04.5451	43°01.5378	135°04.3950	2676	231,5	AGT	24.08.2010
B5-11	43°01.7306	135°05.0794	43°01.6169	135°04.9673	2651	144,5	AGT	24.08.2010
B6-8	43°10.2030	135°00.9159	43°10.0139	135°00.8299	1014	144,5	WT	25.08.2010
B6-9	43°09.3779	135°00.5645	43°09.4745	135°00.5842	1075	108,7	AGT	25.08.2010
B6-10	43°10.0885	135°00.8486	43°10.1569	135°00.8624	1026	88,9	AGT	25.08.2010
B7-8	43°13.5215	135°04.3071	43°13.6778	135°04.4447	532	198,8	WT	25.08.2010
C1-10	42°26.4330	133°08.4329	42°26.4502	133°08.7357	2750	314,8	AGT	27.08.2010
C1-11	42°26.4410	133°08.4800	42°26.4870	133°08.3909	2787	465,5	AGT	27.08.2010
C3-9	42°01.5676	133°09.4601	42°01.4603	133°09.7383	3404	256,8	AGT	29.08.2010
C3-10	42°01.4567	133°08.8196	42°01.2001	133°08.8477	3410	250,0	AGT	29.08.2010
D1-9	41°29.4109	131°47.1928	41°29.1992	131°47.1213	3354	370,4	AGT	31.08.2010
D1-10	41°27.6003	131°47.4004	41°27.3298	131°47.3681	3357	276,6	AGT	31.08.2010
D2-9	42°05.9640	131°19.4615	42°06.0733	131°19.4347	2629	164,2	AGT	01.09.2010
D2-10	42°06.7346	131°20.4442	42°06.9080	131°20.5326	2641	207,4	AGT	01.09.2010

Composition of catches in terms of sediment/substrate in the trawl and animals caught differed strongly with depths: samples from shallower stations and the investigated sea-mount (B2-5, B2-6) often brought forth a higher amount of stones and also larger animals than those from deeper stations, which usually contained a lot of fine sedimentary material and few larger animals (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Examples for different hauls: a) Station B2-5 on the sea-mountain, rocky substrate, depth: 1699 m; b) muddy sample from station C3-9, depth: 3404 m; c) haul from station A3-8 with very few substrate caught, depth: 1644 m; d) rich crinoids catch from shallow station B7-8, depth: 532 m; e) asteroidean from A2-8, depth: 582 m; f) polychaetes from the abyssal, station A7-10, depth: 3213 m.

From the 23 trawls, about 61 taxa could preliminarily be recognized (see Appendix). These showed some characteristics in their distribution (but note, due to the open net, not only benthic organisms were caught): Highest diversity of megafauna was found on the shallowest stations, while the deep-sea hosted only a very poor fauna that was dominated by polynoid polychaetes. On shallow stations, several species of echinoderms, including asteroidea (Fig. 2e) and sometimes crinoids *Heliometra* sp. (see Fig. 2d) were dominant, usually accompanied by large

crabs of the species *Chionoecetes japonicus* (see Fig. 2 a/c). Also, large shrimps, mainly of the species cf. *Pandalus borealis*, occurred. Stations between about 1000 to 2000 m showed very small benthic colonization, usually composed of the above-mentioned shallow-water taxa, which there occurred in much lower densities. Below 2000 m, a very poor deep-sea fauna occurs, mainly composed of polynoid polychaetes (Fig. 2f) and pectenid bivalves. Within these stations, a trend was visible: in shallower depths about 2500 m, pectenids were dominating and polychaetes occurred in slightly lower abundances. On depths around 3300 m, this completely turned, pectenids were almost absent, while polynoids occurred in highest densities.

The species diversity of echinoderms reached its maximum at the shallowest station, it strongly decreased towards the bathyal and abyssal depths. At depths more than 1699 m the only echinoderms were ophiuroids *Ophiura* sp. (same as at the shallower stations) and holothuroids *Myriotrochus* sp. No specific deep-sea echinoderm fauna was found in the abyssal of the Sea of Japan. A possible explanation could be that shallow straits, connecting the Sea of Japan with other water bodies, display a barrier for colonization of the Sea of Japan.

A remarkable feature in faunal composition was the high density of scaphopods at the shallow station B7-8 (532 m), where 59 individuals were found. This station was characterized by sediment which was made up of a high amount of soft material mixed with stones. The only other station which yielded scaphopods (two hauls, 7 and 12 specimens) was located at the sea-mount (B2-5, B2-6, at about 1700 m), characterized by a relatively similar substrate.

The deep-sea revealed certain homogeneity, while the shallower stations showed some differences between each other (compare Appendix). This is especially true for the shallowest stations at about 500 m, which have been sampled with two trawls only and might therefore be considered as under-sampled, particularly in regard to their high diversity. Another biocoenosis composition was found on the sea-mount sampled (trawl B2-5 and B2-6). More stone-attached animals were found compared to other stations sampled at similar depths.

From our preliminary results it seems likely, that, in contrast to the species diversity, no strong decrease in individual counts with increasing depth exists. The deep-sea of the Sea of Japan seems to be an environment with low biodiversity and high abundances of few possibly specialized species, for example the carnivorous polynoid polychaetes.

In general, the findings of the megafauna caught by our trawls support the expectation that the deep-sea fauna of the Sea of Japan is rather poor. Only few elements of common deep-sea megafauna could so far be recognized. Taxa like hexactinellid sponges, cladorhizid sponges, and holothurians were almost completely absent in the deepest stations.

Appendix: Full preliminary taxa list of trawls. Numbers give total catch, “c.” means estimates, “x” shows presence of uncounted specimens

Station:		A2-8	A3-8	A3-9	A6-6	A7-7	A7-10	B2-5	B2-6	B5-9	B5-10	B5-11	B6-8	B6-9	B6-10	B7-8	C1-10	C1-11	C3-9	C3-10	D1-9	D1-10	D2-9	D2-10	
Gear:		AGT	AGT	AGT	WT	WT	AGT	WT	WT	WT	AGT	AGT	WT	AGT	AGT	WT	AGT	AGT	AGT	AGT	AGT	AGT	AGT	AGT	
Depth [m]:		582	1623	1566	2481	3369	3213	1699	1705	2350	2676	2651	1014	1075	1026	532	2750	2787	3404	3410	3354	3357	2629	2641	
Calculated trawled distance [m]		570,4	539,5	344,5	293,9	414,8	447,6	321,0	566,7	242,0	231,5	144,5	144,5	108,7	88,9	198,8	314,8	465,5	256,8	250,0	370,4	276,6	164,2	207,4	
Porifera	indet.	c. 25						c.28	13		3 x													1	
Porifera	Cladorhizidae indet.							30	16																
Cnidaria	Hydrozoa indet.							19	4																
Cnidaria	Actinia indet.	c. 10	1		1			3	4			1							4		c. 50	c. 50	c. 100	c. 50	
Cnidaria	Antozoa indet.				1											c. 5									
Cnidaria	cf. <i>Aurelia</i> sp.																1				1	1			
Ctenophora	indet.																	2							
Bryozoa	indet.	c. 20			1																				
Brachiopoda	cf. <i>Laqueus vancauveniensis</i>																								
Polychaeta	indet.	c. 20	c. 10		1			69	90	10	c. 200	x					c. 200								
Polychaeta	Polynoidae						c. 100				15														
Polychaeta	<i>Aphrodite</i> sp.																								
Chaetognatha	cf. <i>Sagitta elegans</i>			2																					
Nemertini	cf. <i>Tortus tokmakovae</i>									2	4	1					c. 5								
Sipunculida	indet.						c. 10																		
Sipunculida	<i>Golfingia margaritacea margaritacea</i>														1										
Nematoda	indet.							3																	
Scaphopoda	indet.							7	12																
Bivalvia	indet.	4									c. 10	x	x	x		1	c. 100								
Bivalvia	<i>Yoldia</i> sp.	5											2												
Bivalvia	<i>Yoldiella</i> sp.													2	4	4									
Bivalvia	<i>Cuspidaria</i> sp.													5	1	6									
Bivalvia	Pectenidae indet.							7		45							1	c. 200					60	c. 100	
Bivalvia	<i>Nucula</i> sp.																3								
Bivalvia	<i>Thyasira</i> sp.																	c. 50							
Gastropoda	indet.	6											x				40						30		
Gastropoda	Opisthobranchia indet.											1		1											
Gastropoda	<i>Buccinum bayani</i>												1												
Gastropoda	Buccinidae indet.													4	1	7									
Gastropoda	Patellidae indet.																								
Gastropoda	Nudibranchia indet.	1				4					1	1													
Cephalopoda	cf. <i>Loligo</i> sp.																		1						
Crustacea	indet.									5		x													
Crustacea	Copepoda indet.						7				1														
Crustacea	Amphipoda indet.										1	1		2	3		1		1					2	c. 10
Crustacea	Cumacea indet.													8											
Crustacea	Euphausiacea indet.		c. 100	2																				2	
Crustacea	Mysidacea indet.		4																						
Crustacea	Decapoda indet.																								
Crustacea	Natantia indet.	c. 30											c. 25	17	16	5				4					
Crustacea	Brachyura indet.	c. 10																							
Crustacea	<i>Chionoecetes japonicus</i>		18	21				11	4																
Crustacea	Tanaidacea indet.							7																	
Crustacea	Isopoda indet.							1																	
Echinodermata	indet.																								
Echinodermata	Asteroidea indet.	3													13	20	c. 350								
Echinodermata	Asteroidea, Benthoplect	3																							
Echinodermata	Asteroidea, Asteroidea																								
Echinodermata	Asteroidea, Goniasteric	8						1																	
Echinodermata	<i>Ctenodiscus crispatus</i>	376		92								c. 25	30			7									
Echinodermata	<i>Asterias</i> sp.	5																							
Echinodermata	<i>Crossaster</i> sp.	4																							
Echinodermata	Echinoidea indet.																								
Echinodermata	<i>Strongylocentrotus</i> sp.	1																							
Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea indet.	8								5	15	10					c. 1000		11	c. 45				8	c. 20
Echinodermata	<i>Heliometra</i> sp.																								
Echinodermata	<i>Molpadia musculus</i>																								
Echinodermata	<i>Myriotrochus</i> sp.																								2
Tunicata	Ascidia indet.							234	50			5													
Osteichthyes	<i>Lycodes tanakae</i>													1											
Osteichthyes	<i>Malacocottus zonurus</i>	1																							
Osteichthyes	<i>Bothrocara hollandi</i>	14	17	38									1		1										
Osteichthyes	<i>Careproctus</i> sp.							1																	
Mammalia	Cetacea indet.																								

References:

- Brandt, A., Barthel, D., 1995. An improved supra- and epibenthic sledge for catching Peracarida (Crustacea, Malacostraca). *Ophelia* 43 (1): 15-23.
- Brenke, N., 2005. An epibenthic sledge for operations on marine soft bottom and bedrock. *Marine Technology Society Journal* 39(2), 10-19.
- Derjugin, K.M., 1933. Pacific expedition of the State Hydrological Institute 1932. *Issledovaniya morey SSSR* 19, 5–36.
- Derjugin, K.M. 1939, Zones and biocenoses of the Peter the Great Bay (the Sea of Japan). *M.* 115–142.
- Golovan O.A., 2007. *Mirabilicoxa kussakini* sp. nov., a new species of Desmosomatidae (Crustacea, Isopoda, Asellota) from the Sea of Japan // *Biologia morya*, Vol. 33, No. 6, pp. 408-416.
- Gurjanova, E.F., 1936. Contribution to the fauna of Isopoda of the Pacific Ocean. III. New species in collections of the Hydrological Institute, collected in 1932. *Issledovaniya morei SSSR*. 22, 25–35.
- Levenstein, R.Y., Pasternak, F.A., 1973. On the polychete fauna of the Aleutian, Japanese and Indo-Bornean trenches from the Pacific Ocean. *Trudy Instituta Okeanologii, Akademia Nauk SSSR* 91, 128–135.
- Levenstein, R.Y., Pasternak, F.A., 1976. Quantitative distribution of the bottom fauna in Japan Sea. *Trudy Instituta Okeanologii, Akademia Nauk SSSR*, 99, 197-210.
- Pasternak, F.A., Levenstein, R.Y., 1978. New data on the distribution of deep-water bottom fauna in the Sea of Japan. *Okeanologiya*, 18, 903-908. (In Russian).
- Tabachnik, K.R., 1991. Hexactinellid sponges from the Sea of Japan with description of a new species of *Scyphidium* genus. *Zoologichesky zhurnal* 70: 129-131.
- Uschakov, P.V., 1955. Polychaeta of the Far Eastern Seas of the USSR. *Keys to the fauna of the USSR*, 56, 1-445. (In Russian).
- Vinogradova N.G., Filatova, Z.A., 1983 Investigation of the deep-sea fauna. Research vessel “Vitjaz” and her expeditions 1949–1979 гг. Moscow: Nauka. 236–254.